

**Additions and corrections to the Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera,
vol. 6/1, 2020. Revised and Updated Second Edition. Chrysomeloidea
I (Vesperiidae, Disteniidae, Cerambycidae). Part II**

M.L. Danilevsky¹, G. Tavakilian²

¹A.N. Severtsov Institute of Ecology and Evolution of the Russian Academy of Sciences
Leninsky prospect 33, Moscow 119071 Russia
e-mail: danilevskym1@rambler.ru, danilevsky@cerambycidae.net

²Laboratory of Entomology, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle de Paris
Buffon str., 45, Paris F-75005 France
e-mail: gerard.tavakilian@mnhn.fr

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Abstract: Many misprints, wrong combinations, wrong original combinations, wrong geographical records, wrong references, wrong status of certain names, wrong synonyms, wrong authorships and dates of certain names, wrong spelling of several names, wrong determinations and so on are fixed. Sometimes valid names were published as synonyms. Sometimes unavailable names were published as available. Several times certain names were published twice in different combinations or even in one genus. Missing names, geographical data and references are added. New geographical records are also published.

A female of *Strangalia 4-fasciata* var. *notatipennis* Pic, 1897b from “Trébizonde (Pic’s collection in Muséum national d’Histoire naturelle, Paris) is designated here as a lectotype. *Hesperophanes tomentosus* Lucas, 1842 is regarded as a synonym of *Trichoferus griseus* (Fabricius, 1793). *Xylotrechus ilamensis* Holzschuh, 1979a is recorded for Russia (Dagestan). Georgian populations of *Parmena aurora* Danilevsky, 1980 (described from Talysh) are now accepted as *P. striatopunctata* Sama, 1994f (described from Artvin). *Anoplophora grisea* Tippmann, 1953 = *A. birmanica* Hüdepohl, 1990, **syn. nov.** distributed in Myanmar and Assam. Several Albanian local forms of *Dorcadion aethiops* are regarded as subspecies: *D. a. balthasari* Heyrovský, 1962 (Shkodër, Tirana, Sauk); *D. a. laevipunctatum* Breuning, 1944 (Mali i Thate); *D. a. maderi* Breit, 1923 (Vora, Kruja, Elbasan); *D. a. sterbai* Breuning, 1944 (Moskopolje = Voskopoje, Kulmak), **stat. nov.** *Dorcadion kurdistanum rufulipes* Breuning, 1971c [“nö Bingol”] is accepted as a valid name. *Dorcadion serouense* Kadlec, 2006b is recorded from Iraq. *Dorcadion kusnezovi* Jakovlev, 1906b is accepted as a valid name, and the area of *D. mystacinum* Ballion, 1878 is restricted to the environs of

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

the type locality - Kuldzha (Yining). *Leiopus linnei* Wallin, Nylander & Kvamme, 2009 was described before as *Cerambyx taeniatus* Gmelin, 1790 from Siberia, so *L. taeniatus* (Gmelin, 1790) = *L. linnei* Wallin, Nylander & Kvamme, 2009, **syn. nov.** A pair of synonyms are accepted: *Exocentrus nobuoi okinawensis* Breuning & K. Ohbayashi, 1966 = *Ex. paraguttulatus* Breuning & Chûjô, 1971. *Phytoecia (Pilemia) evae* D. Marklund & S. Marklund, 2014 has no peculiar characters, so: *Phytoecia (Pseudopilemia) hirsutula* (Frölich, 1793) = *Ph. (P.) evae* D. Marklund & S. Marklund, 2014, **syn. nov.** *Oberea coreana* var. *licenti* Pic, 1939b = *O. scutellaroides* Breuning, 1947c, **syn. nov.** *Agapanthia kirbyi* (Gyllenhal, 1817) from Balkans, Tanscaucasia, and Near East is accepted as *A. kirbyi zawadskyi* Fairmaire, 1866b (= *A. kirbyi valandovensis* Sláma, 2015c, **syn. nov.**).

Introduction

New attentive study of the published version of the second edition of the Catalogue (Danilevsky, 2020) allowed to continue corrections published before (Danilevsky, 2021). Many mistakes, as well as missing names and references were newly discovered, though many wrong cases fixed now were published before in the first edition of the Catalogue (Löbl & Smetana, 2010).

The references to the present article include only the publications absent in the references to the Catalogue. The references inside the text of the present article to the publications included in the references to the Catalogue have same letters after the number of the year as in the Catalogue.

Corrected positions are underlined.

All correction and additions are reflected by G. Tavakilian (author) & H. Chevillotte (software) (2021) - (<http://titan.gbif.fr>) and in the Catalogue of Palaearctic Chrysomeloidea (Vesperidae, Disteniidae, Cerambycidae) by M. Danilevsky (author) & M. Lazarev (software) (2022) - (<http://cerambycidae.net>).

Results

p. 3

printed:

Anoplisthes balcanicus Slama, 2010 is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Anoplisthes halodendri balcanicus* Slama, 2010.

must be:

Anoplistes balcanicus Slama, 2010 is downgraded to subspecies rank: *Anoplistes halodendri balcanicus* Slama, 2010.

p. 9

printed:

Tetropium obscuripenne Semenov, 1907c was originally introduced as *Tetropium tjanshanicum* ab. *obscuripenn*e Semenov, 1907c and so unavailabe.

must be:

Tetropium obscuripenne Semenov, 1907c was originally introduced as *Tetropium tjanshanicum* ab. *obscuripenn*is Semenov, 1907c and so unavailable.

p. 54

must be added to #161:

The validity of *Ch. sparsus* (Reitter, 1886) is not evident (color form of *gratiosus*?), as it is sympatric with *Ch. gratiosus* in South Turkey.

p. 57

must be added to #179:

In fact, the statement by Lin et al. (2017): on “the absence of distinct lateral elytral carinae” in *E. ocelota* was wrong. Lateral elytral carinae in *E. ocelota* are very strong, and the species must be considered as *Eutetrapha*.

p. 65

printed:

New synonyms were proposed by Kasatkin (2018): *Phytoecia (Pseudopilemia) hirsutula* (Frölich, 1793) = *Ph. (P.) buglanica* D.Marklund & S.Marklund, 2014. The status of *Pilemia vagecarinata* Pic, 1952a rests uncertain.

must be:

New synonyms were proposed by Kasatkin (2018): *Phytoecia (Pseudopilemia) hirsutula* (Frölich, 1793) = *Ph. (P.) buglanica* D. Marklund & S. Marklund, 2014. The status of *Pilemia vagecarinata* Pic, 1952a rests uncertain. *Ph. (P.) evae* D. Marklund & S. Marklund, 2014 neither has any peculiar characters, so: *Phytoecia (Pseudopilemia) hirsutula* (Frölich, 1793) = *Ph. (P.) evae* D. Marklund & S. Marklund, 2014, **syn. nov.**

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 97

printed:

Rhondia placida Heller, 1923b was recorded for Mongolia by Xu et al. (2007).

must be:

Rhondia placida Heller, 1923b was recorded for Inner Mongolia by Xu et al. (2007).

p. 100

printed:

Xylotrechus stebbingi Gahan, 1906 was recorded for Croatia by Brelih et al. (2006).

must be:

Xylotrechus stebbingi Gahan, 1906 was recorded for Croatia by Brelih et al. (2006); for Portugal by Grosso-Silva (2019).

p. 110

printed:

genus ***Bandar Lameere, 1912a: 144*** type species *Prinobius pascoei* Lansberge, 1884

maedai Komiya 2016: 27 **A: AP**

pascoei formosae Gressitt, 1938b: 147 (*Macrotoma*) **A: JA (Ryukyus) TAI**

must be:

genus ***Bandar Lameere, 1912a: 144*** type species *Prinobius pascoei* Lansberge, 1884

maedai Komiya 2016: 27 **A: AP**

pascoei formosae Gressitt, 1938b: 147 (*Macrotoma*) **A: JA (Ryukyus) TAI**

p. 111

According to Bouyer (2016), *Macrotoma coelaspis* White, 1853a is a valid name of an African species.

p. 115

printed:

genus ***Polyarthron Audinet-Serville, 1832: 189*** type species *Prionus pectinicornis*

Fabricius, 1793

must be:

genus ***Polyarthron Audinet-Serville, 1832: 189*** type species *Prionus pectinicornis*

Fabricius, 1793

Neynis Gistel, 1848: xi [unnecessary substitute name]

p. 118

printed:

unilamellatum Pu, 1987: 90 (*Prionus*) **A: XIZ**

must be:

unilamellatus Pu, 1987: 90 (*Prionus*) **A: XIZ**

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 120

birubrosignata Pic, 1941b: 1 (*Leptura*) - misspelling of *birubronotata* Pic, 1941b: 1 (*Leptura*) - was published two times (under *Anastrangalia dubia dubia* and under *A. d. moreana*).

L. d. var. *birubronotata* Pic, 1941b was described from “Grand-Chartreuse”, so it was a synonym of *A. dubia dubia*.

p. 120

printed:

planeti Pic, 1945b: 5

must be:

planeti Pic, 1945b: 5 (*Leptura*)

p. 121

Leptura melanura, Ström, 1765 was not a new name but wrong interpretation of *Leptura melanura* Linnaeus, 1758.

p. 121

ratchaensis Pic, 1911: 4 (*Leptura*) - a synonym of *Anastrangalia dubia melanota* was missing.

p. 121

printed:

semiangustata Reitter, 1898d: 193 (*Leptura*)

must be:

semisanguinea Reitter, 1898d: 193 (*Leptura*)

p. 122

bursensis Jureček, 1931: 124 (*Leptura*) - a synonym of *Anoplodera rufipes rufipes* (Schaller, 1783) was missing.

p. 122

printed:

baicalensis Pic, 1907a: 6 (*Leptura*)

must be:

baikalensis Pic, 1907a: 6 (*Leptura*)

p. 127

missing name:

Grammoptera ustulata var. *semirufescens* Pic, 1947a: 4

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 128

printed:

contracta Bates, 1884a: 223 (*Strangalia*) A: JA JIX
mediolineata Pic, 1954: 13 (*Strangalia*)
ohbayashii Matsushita, 1933b: 220 (*Strangalia*)
tamanukii Hayashi, 1959b: 61 (*Pygostrangalia*)

and

sozanensis Mitono, 1938: 17 (*Strangalia*) A: FUJ GUA GUX HUN JIX TAI ZHE
lineatocollis Gressitt, 1937b: 319 (*Strangalina*)
simillima Hayashi & Villiers, 1989: 1 #135

must be:

contracta Bates, 1884a: 223 (*Strangalia*) A: JA JIX
lineatocollis Gressitt, 1937b: 319 (*Strangalina*)
mediolineata Pic, 1954: 13 (*Strangalia*)
ohbayashii Matsushita, 1933b: 220 (*Strangalia*)
tamanukii Hayashi, 1959b: 61 (*Pygostrangalia*)

and

sozanensis Mitono, 1938: 17 (*Strangalia*) A: FUJ GUA GUX HUN JIX TAI ZHE
simillima Hayashi & Villiers, 1989: 1 #135

p. 129

printed:

tyrolensis Pic, 1914b: 5

must be:

tyrolensis Reineck, 1913: 300

p. 130

printed:

genus *Laoleptura*

must be:

genus *Laoleptura*

p. 133

Strangalia 4-fasciata var. *notatipennis* Pic, 1897b was described on the base of two syntypes (females): from “Trèbizonde” and from “Suisse”. A female (Pic’s collection in Muséum national d’Histoire naturelle, Paris) from “Trèbizonde” is designated here as lectotype, so var. *notatipennis* Pic, 1897b belongs to *S. q. lederi* Gang.

p. 137

printed:

bisquadrastigmatus Pic, 1915a: 29 (*Leptura*)

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

must be:

bisquadristigma Pic, 1915a: 29 (*Leptura*)

p. 137 and p. 145

printed:

atrosuturalis Pic, 1915a: 38 (*Leptura*)

(p.137 as a synonym of *erraticus* Dalman, 1817a)

(p.145 as a synonym of *septempunctata* Fabricus, 1793)

First case was wrong.

p. 138

printed:

rosinae Pic, 1914c: 13 (*Leptura*)

must be:

rosinae Pic, 1901b: 11 (*Leptura*)

p. 147

dufourii Lecomte, 1926: 168 (*Leptura*) - a synonym of *Stictoleptura rubra rubra* (Linnaeus, 1758) was missing.

p. 150

printed:

brunnescens Balbi, 1892: 49

must be:

brunnescens Balbi, 1892: 49 (*Leptura*)

p. 154

printed:

vittatus Gmelin, 1790: 1865 (*Stenocorus*)

must be:

vittatus Gmelin, 1790: 1865 (*Cerambyx*)

p. 155-156

printed:

bifasciata bifasciata Olivier, 1800: 23 (*Leptura*) [HN] A: ES FE GAN HEB HEI JIL
LIA MG NC NMO QIN SC SCH XIZ

must be:

bifasciata bifasciata Olivier, 1795: 23 (*Leptura*) [HN] A: ES FE GAN HEB HEI JIL
LIA MG NC NMO QIN SC SCH XIZ

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 174

printed:

genus *Pseudogaurotina* Plavilstshikov, 1958b: 722 type species *Gaurotes splendens* Jakovlev, 1893

splendens Jakovlev, 1893a: 444 (*Gaurotes*) **A: ES ?MG**

magnifica Plavilstshikov, 1958b: 720 (*Gaurotes*) **A: FE**

excellens Brancsik, 1874: 230 (*Pachyta*) **E: PL RO SK UK**

robertae Pesarini & Sabbadini, 1997: 99 **A: SCH**

must be:

genus *Pseudogaurotina* Plavilstshikov, 1958b: 722 type species *Gaurotes splendens* Jakovlev, 1893

excellens Brancsik, 1874: 230 (*Pachyta*) **E: PL RO SK UK**

magnifica Plavilstshikov, 1958b: 720 (*Gaurotes*) **A: FE**

robertae Pesarini & Sabbadini, 1997: 99 **A: SCH**

splendens Jakovlev, 1893a: 444 (*Gaurotes*) **A: ES ?MG**

p. 175

printed:

infasciatum Pic, 1910d: 18

must be:

infasciatum Pic, 1898a: 3

p. 176

printed:

placida Heller, 1923b: 72 **A: HUB MG SCH SHA #490**

must be:

placida Heller, 1923b: 72 **A: HUB NMO SCH SHA #490**

p. 180

printed:

cremarius Holzschuh, 1999: 6 (*Teledapus*) **A: SHA**

must be:

cremarius Holzschuh, 1999: 6 (*Teledapus*) **A: SHA**

p. 180

printed:

koltzei Heyden, 1887c: 304 (*Brachyta*) **A: ES FE GUA HEI JA LIA NC NMO SC**

must be:

koltzei Heyden, 1887a: 304 (*Brachyta*) **A: ES FE GUA HEI JA LIA NC NMO SC**

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 190

printed:

gressitty Miroshnikov & Lin, 2014: 117 A: XIX

must be:

gressitti Miroshnikov & Lin, 2014: 117 A: XIX

p. 191

printed:

tomentosum atticum Ganglbauer, 1882: 743 E: BH BU CR CY FRi GR IT MA A:
AB CY JO IS SY TR

must be:

tomentosum atticum Ganglbauer, 1882: 743 E: BH BU CR FRi GR IT MA A: AB
CY JO IS LE SY TR

p. 191-192

printed (p. 191):

colobothoides Bates, 1884a: 235 (*Aglaophis*) A: FE JA NC NE QIN SC #400

angustefasciatus Heyden, 1884: 297 (*Aglaophis*)

arakawai Kano, 1933a: 276

and (p. 192)

arakawae amamiensis Fujita, 1980: 14 A: JA (Ryukyus)

arakawae arakawae Kano, 1933a: 276 (*Aglaophis*) A: JA

arakawae kumagensis Fujita, 1980: 14 A: JA

First case was wrong.

p. 195

printed:

thoracicus Podaný, 1980: 232 (*Polyzonus*)

must be:

thoracicus Podaný, 1980: 232 (*Polyzonus*)

p. 195

printed:

inexpectatum Podaný, 1971: 293 A: NO GUX

must be:

inexpectatum Podaný, 1971: 293 A: NO GUX

p. 198, 378

printed:

[HM]

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

must be:

[HN]

pp. 203-204

ater Fisher, 1936: 176 (*Coloborhombus*) was mentioned two times; in fact, it was a synonym of *Scalenus drescheri* (Fisher, 1936).

pp. 205, 209

printed (p. 205):

genus *Gerdberndia* Holzschuh, 1982a: 71 type species *Gerdberndia atricolor* Holzschuh, 1982

atricolor Holzschuh, 1982a: 71 A: NP

ferrocyanea Hayashi, 1979: 87 (*Prosemanotus*) A: BT NP

nubigena Semenov & Plavilstshikov, 1936: 391 (*Rhopalopus*) A: NP ?QIN (Gorin-tshu River)
(p. 209)

nubigena Semenov & Plavilstshikov, 1936: 391 (*Rhopalopus*) A: XIZ
as *Ropalopus*

Second position was wrong.

p. 207

printed:

luridus Olivier, 1800: 23 (*Calidium*)

must be:

luridus Olivier, 1800: 23 (*Callidium*)

p. 208

printed:

luridus Paykull, 1800: 87 (*Callidium*)

must be:

luridus Paykull, 1800: 87 (*Callidium*) [HN]

p. 209

printed:

sanguineum Linnaeus, 1758: 396 E: AL AU BE BH BU BY CR CT CZ DE ?EN FI
FR GB GE GR HU IR IT ?LA LS LT LU MD ME NL NR NT PL PT RO SB SK
SL SP ST SV SZ TR UK N: AG TU A: AB AR GG IN SY TR

must be:

sanguineum Linnaeus, 1758: 396 (*Cerambyx*) E: AL AU BE BH BU BY CR CT CZ
DE ?EN FI FR GB GE GR HU IR IT ?LA LS LT LU MD ME NL NR NT PL PT
RO SB SK SL SP ST SV SZ TR UK N: AG TU A: AB AR GG IN SY TR

p. 209

Ropalopus clavipes is absent in Latvia (D. Telnov, personal communication).

pp. 212, 213

printed (p. 212):

flavipes Fabricius, 1792b: 327 (*Callidium*) **A: GUA HKG TAI AFR AUR NTR ORR**
ambiguum Newman, 1842a: 246 (*Arhopalus*)

and (p. 213):

unicolor unicolor Fabricius, 1787: 147 (*Saperda*) **A: JA “North India” AUS**
ambiguum Newman, 1842a: 246 (*Arhopalus*)

The second case was wrong.

p. 213

printed:

zeylanicum Yokoi, 2015: 198 **A: HKG ORR**

must be:

zeylanicum White, 1855: 246 **A: HKG ORR**
basilanum Pic, 1943d: 6

p. 213

printed:

setigerus Sharp, 1878: 203 (*Sotenus*)

must be:

setiger Sharp, 1878: 203 (*Sotenus*)

p. 216

printed:

genus *Derolus* Gahan, 1891a: 26 type species *Hammaticherus mauritanicus*

Buquet, 1840

Capnocerambyx Reitter, 1894g: 356 type species *Hammaticherus mauritanicus* Buquet, 1840

Mimoderolus Pic, 1933a: 11 type species *Aeolesthes (Mimoderolus) uniformis* Pic, 1933 **#207**

must be:

genus *Derolus* Gahan, 1891a: 26 type species *Hammaticherus mauritanicus* Buquet, 1840

Capnocerambyx Reitter, 1894g: 356 type species *Hammaticherus mauritanicus* Buquet, 1840

According to Miroshnikov (2018c), *Tapinolachnus* Thomson, 1864 (Oriental taxon) = *Mimoderolus* Pic, 1933a.

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 217

printed:

genus *Dymasius* J. Thomson, 1864: 234 type species *Dymasius strigosus*
J. Thomson, 1864 (= *Cerambyx macilentus* Pascoe, 1859)

must be:

genus *Dymasius* J. Thomson, 1864: 234 type species *Dymasius strigosus*
J. Thomson, 1864.

According to Miroshnikov (2017), *Dymasius macilentus* (Pascoe, 1859) is a valid name.

Miroshnikov A. I. 2017: The longicorn beetle tribe Cerambycini Latreille, 1802 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Cerambycinae) in the fauna of Asia. 1. New or little-known taxa, mainly from Indochina and Borneo, with reviews of some genera. *Caucasian Entomological Bulletin* **13** (2): 161-233, 461 figs.

pp. 218, 219

printed (p. 218):

genus *Massicus* Pascoe, 1867a: 319 [RN] type species *Cerambyx pascoei*
J. Thomson, 1857b **#458**

Conothorax J. Thomson, 1864: 230 [HN] type species *Cerambyx pascoei* J. Thomson, 1857b
Falsomassicus Pic, 1946a: 7 type species *Falsomassicus theresae* Pic, 1946

and (p. 219):

genus *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861: 194 type species *Cerambyx paris*
Wiedemann, 1821 **#458**

Mallambyx Bates, 1873: 152 type species *Mallambyx japonicus* Bates, 1873
(= *Neocerambyx raddei* Blessig, 1872)

must be (p. 218):

genus *Massicus* Pascoe, 1867a: 319 [RN] type species *Cerambyx pascoei*
J. Thomson, 1857b **#458**

Conothorax J. Thomson, 1864: 230 [HN] type species *Cerambyx pascoei* J. Thomson, 1857b

and (p. 219):

genus *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861: 194 type species *Cerambyx paris*
Wiedemann, 1821 **#458**

Falsomassicus Pic, 1946a: 7 type species *Falsomassicus theresae* Pic, 1946

Mallambyx Bates, 1873: 152 type species *Mallambyx japonicus* Bates, 1873
(= *Neocerambyx raddei* Blessig, 1872)

pp. 218, 220

printed (218):

genus *Margites* Gahan, 1891a: 26 type species *Cerambyx egenus* Pascoe, 1858

subgenus *Margites* Gahan, 1891a: 26 type species *Cerambyx egenus* Pascoe, 1858
auratonotatus Pic, 1923e: 7 A: FUJ GUA GUI HEN HUB HUN JIA JIX SCH

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

decepiens Holzschuh, 1989c: 393 **A**: BT

and (p. 220)

genus *Plavichydissus* Pic, 1946b: 107 type species: *Pachydissus semiplicatus* Pic, 1926
#277

decepiens Holzschuh, 1989c: 393 (*Margites*) **A**: BT

First case was wrong.

p. 219

printed:

taiwanus Makihara & Niisato, 2014: 24 (*Massicus*) **A**: TAI

must be:

taiwanus Makihara & Niisato, 2014: 24 **A**: TAI

p. 220

According to Vitali (2011), *Prospilus serraticornis* (Bertoloni, 1855) is a valid name of an African species.

p. 220

Two synonyms of *Neoplocaederus spinicornis* (Fabricius, 1781) were missing:

pubipennis White, 1853a: 126 (*Hammatocherus*)

denticornis Olivier, 1795: 60 (*Cerambix*)

p. 220

printed:

laosensis Gressitt & Rondon, 1970: 64 **A**: YUN **ORR**

must be:

laosensis Gressitt & Rondon, 1970: 64 (*Aeolesthes*) **A**: YUN **ORR**

p. 226

printed:

annularis Fabricius, 1787: 156 (*Callidium*) **A**: ANH AP FUJ GUA GUI GUX HAI
HEB HEN HKG HP HUB HUN JA JIA JIL JIX LIA NP SC SCH SD SHA TAI
UP XIZ YUN ZHE **NARi NTRi ORR** #127 #280 #366 #390

bidens Weber, 1801: 90 (*Callidium*)

bisbiinterruptus Pic, 1953c: 11

griseopubens Pic, 1943b: 3

must be:

annularis Fabricius, 1787: 156 (*Callidium*) **Ei**: **BE GE SP A**: ANH AP FUJ GUA
GUI GUX HAI HEB HEN HKG HP HUB HUN JA JIA JIL JIX LIA NP SC SCH

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

SD SHA TAI UP XIZ YUN ZHE NARi NTRi ORR #127 #280 #366 #390

bidens Weber, 1801: 90 (*Callidium*)

bisbiinterruptus Pic, 1953c: 11

breveinterruptus Pic, 1953c: 10 (Tonkin)

griseopubens Pic, 1943b: 3

According to Lindhe et al. (2010), *Chlorophorus annularis* is established in Spain, Belgium and Germany; many other records from all over Europe were based on single imported specimens.

p. 227

printed:

curtipennis Pic, 1943a: 1 (*Chlorophorus* - misprint, not available name) A: CH

must be:

curtipennis Pic, 1943a: 1 A: CH

p. 226

missing *Chlorophorus* name:

amoenus Castelnau & Gory, 1841: 88 (*Clytus*) A: YE AFR

It was recorded for Jemen by Villiers (1977: 167).

p. 227

Chlorophorus reductus v. *brevejunctus* Pic, 1943a: 1 - a synonym of *Chlorophorus douei* (Chevrolat, 1863) was missing.

p. 227

printed:

ahatodae Chatterjee & Misra, 1971: 91

must be:

ahatodae Chatterjee & Misra, 1971: 91

p. 227

Chlorophorus insignifer v. *robustus* Pic, 1920d: 16 - a synonym of *Chlorophorus eleodes* (Fairmaire, 1889a) was missing.

p. 227

missing *Chlorophorus* name:

curvatofasciatus Aurivillius, 1922a: 410 A: JA TAI ORR

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

It was recorded for Taiwan and Japan by Hua (2002: 201) and Lin M.-Y. [Meiying] & Yang X.-K. (2019: 144).

p. 228

Clytanthus verbasci v. *clermonti* Pic, 1921a: 13 - a synonym of *Chlorophorus faldermanni* (Falderman, 1837) was missing.

Leptura lamda Schrank, 1776: 67 - a synonym of *Chlorophorus figuratus* (Scopoli, 1763) was missing.

Clytus rugulosus Broun, 1880: 588 - a synonym of *Chlorophorus glabromaculatus glabromaculatus* (Goeze, 1777) was missing.

Chlorophorus pilosus var. *thoracicus* Rungs, 1947: 100 - a synonym of *Chlorophorus glabromaculatus glaucus* (Fabricius, 1781) was missing.

p. 229

printed:

multijunctus Pic, 1943a: 1 (*Chlorophorus* - misprint, not available name)

must be:

multijunctus Pic, 1943a: 1 (*Chlorophorus* - misprint, not available name)

p. 230

Chlorophorus quatuordecimmaculatus var. *anticeconfluens* Plavilstshikov, 1927b:107 - a synonym of *Ch. quatuordecimmaculatus* (Chevrolat, 1863) was missing.

Caloclytus rubricollis var. *andamanicus* Gahan, 1906: 265 - a synonym of *Ch. rubricollis* (Laporte & Gory, 1841) was missing.

p. 230

missing *Chlorophorus* name:

oppositus Chevrolat, 1863: 304 (*Anthoboscus*) A: ?TAI

The taxon was described from “Chine sept.”. It was recorded for Taiwan by Özdikmen (2022: 670). The status of the name is doubtful (Holzschuh, 2020: 50).

p. 231, 235 and 247

printed (p. 231):

sartor O.F. Müller, 1766: 188 (*Cerambyx*) E: AL AU BH BU BY CR CT CZ FR

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

GE GR HU IT KZ ?LA LU MC MD ME PL PT RO SB SK SL SP ST SZ TR UK
A: AB AR CY ?ES GG IN IS JO KZ LE IQ SY TM TR WS #30 #64 #104

achilleae Brahm, 1790: 141 (*Leptura*)
angusticollis Mulsant, 1851a: 123 (*Clytus*)
corsicus Chevrolat, 1882: 58 (*Clytus*)

and (p. 235):

rhamni bellieri Gautier des Cottés, 1862: 77 E: FR GE IT PT SP SZ
ferruginipes Pic, 1891b: 26
siculus Wagner, 1927b: 93 [HN]

and (p. 247):

gracilipes Faldermann, 1835: 436 (*Clytus*) E: BY CT ?LT NT PL ?RO ST ?UK A:
BEI ES FE HEI JIL KZ MG NC NMO SC WS
angusticollis Mulsant, 1851a: 123 (*Clytus*)
rosinae Pic, 1935d: 15 (*Chlorophorus*)
sachalinensis Matsumura, 1911: 139 (*Clytanthus*)
tenuicornis Fairmaire, 1888b: 142 (*Clytus*)

must be (p. 231):

sartor O.F. Müller, 1766: 188 (*Cerambyx*) E: AL AU BH BU BY CR CT CZ FR
GE GR HU IT KZ ?LA LU MC MD ME PL PT RO SB SK SL SP ST SZ TR UK
A: AB AR CY ?ES GG IN IS JO KZ LE IQ SY TM TR WS #30 #64 #104
achilleae Brahm, 1790: 141 (*Leptura*)
angusticollis Mulsant, 1851a: 123 (*Clytus*)

and (p. 235):

rhamni bellieri Gautier des Cottés, 1862: 77 E: FR GE IT PT SP SZ
ferruginipes Pic, 1891b: 26
siculus Wagner, 1927b: 93 [HN]
corsicus Chevrolat, 1882: 58 (*Clytus*)

and (p. 247)

gracilipes Faldermann, 1835: 436 (*Clytus*) E: BY CT ?LT NT PL ?RO ST
?UK A: BEI ES FE HEI JIL KZ MG NC NMO SC WS
rosinae Pic, 1935d: 15 (*Chlorophorus*)
sachalinensis Matsumura, 1911: 139 (*Clytanthus*)
tenuicornis Fairmaire, 1888b: 142 (*Clytus*)

p. 232

printed:

varius varius O. F. Müller, 1766: 188 (*Leptura*) E: AE AL AU BH BU BY CR CT
CZ FR GBi GE GR HU IT LS LT MA MC MD ME NL PL RO SB SK SL SP ST
SZ TR UK A: AB AR GG KZ TR WS #345 #400
c-duplex Scopoli, 1786: 46 (*Stenocorus*)
ferrugineus Mulsant, 1839: 87 (*Clytus*)
gammoides Geoffroy, 1785: 81 (*Leptura*)
incanus Plavilstshikov, 1924: 229
mixtornatus Fleischer, 1908: 211 (*Clytanthus*)
strigosus Gmelin, 1790: 1877 (*Leptura*)
venustus Gmelin, 1790: 1856 (*Cerambyx*)
viridicollis Kraatz, 1871b: 410 (*Clytus*)

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

must be:

varius varius O. F. Müller, 1766: 188 (*Leptura*) **E:** AL AU BH BU BY CR CT CZ
FR GBi GE GR HU IT LS LT MA MC MD ME NL PL RO SB SK SL SP ST SZ
TR UK **A:** AB AF AR GG KZ TR WS **#345 #400**

c-duplex Scopoli, 1786: 46 (*Stenocorus*)

ferrugineus Mulsant, 1839: 87 (*Clytus*)

fontanae Hubenthal, 1923: 141 (*Clytanthus*)

gammoides Geoffroy, 1785: 81 (*Leptura*)

incanus Plavilstshikov, 1924: 229

mixtornatus Fleischer, 1908: 211 (*Clytanthus*)

mouinieri Pic, 1950c: 6

nigrofasciatus Goeze, 1777: 507 (*Leptura*)

ornatum Herbst, 1784: 98 (*Callidium*)

strigosus Gmelin, 1790: 1877 (*Leptura*)

venustus Gmelin, 1790: 1856 (*Cerambyx*)

verbasci Linné, 1767 (*Leptura*)

viridicollis Kraatz, 1871b: 410 (*Clytus*)

p. 234

printed:

nigritulus Kraatz, 1879c: 109 **A:** ES FE HEI JIL NC SC

fulvohirsutus Pic, 1904e: 18

must be:

nigritulus Kraatz, 1879c: 109 **A:** ES FE HEI JIL NC SC

fulvohirsutus Pic, 1904e: 18 **A:** FE FE HEI JIL NC SC

p. 234

printed:

rhamni bellieri Gautier des Cottés, 1862: 77 **E:** FR GE IT PT SP SZ

ferruginipes Pic, 1891b: 26

siculus Wagner, 1927b: 93 [HN]

rhamni temesiensis Germar, 1823: 519 (*Callidium*) **E:** AU BU CT CZ GE HU MD RO SK

SL ST TR UK **A:** AB AR CY GG IN IQ IS KZ LE SY TR **#104 #186 #482 #506**

ferruginipes Pic, 1891b: 26

longicollis Reitter, 1904: 82

must be:

rhamni bellieri Gautier des Cottés, 1862: 77 **E:** FR GE IT PT SP SZ

corsicus Chevrolat, 1882: 58 (*Clytus*)

siculus Wagner, 1927b: 93 [HN]

rhamni temesiensis Germar, 1823: 519 (*Callidium*) **E:** AU BU CT CZ GE HU MD RO

SK SL ST TR UK **A:** AB AR CY GG IN IQ IS KZ LE SY TR **#104 #186 #482 #506**

ferruginipes Pic, 1891b: 26

longicollis Reitter, 1904: 82

Clytus rhamni v. *ferruginipes* Pic, 1891 was described from “Turquie”.

p. 239

printed:

mouhouti Pascoe, 1869a: 604 (*Clytanthus*)

must be:

mouhqi Pascoe, 1869a: 604 (*Clytanthus*)

p. 239

Clytus annulus Fabricius, 1801 (South Africa) - a synonym of *Echinocerus floralis* (Pallas, 1773) - was missing (see Kasatkin, 2020).

p. 239

Stenocorus arcuatus, Scopoli, 1772 was not a new name, but wrong application of the name *Leptura arcuata* Linnaeus, 1758 - now *Plagionotus arcuatus* (Linnaeus, 1758).

p. 241

Isotomus speciosus was recorded for Turkey (Tokat) by Adlbauer (1992) and then by a number of Turkish authors.

p. 242

printed:

andrei Fuente, 1908a: 21 (*Plagionotus*) E: PT SP #165

marcaorum López-Colón, 1997: 219 (*Plagionotus*)

marcorum Vives, 2000: 190 [unjustified emendation]

must be:

andrei Fuente, 1908a: 21 (*Plagionotus*) E: PT SP #165

marcaorum López-Colón, 1997: 221 (*Plagionotus*)

marcorum López-Colón, 1998: 311 (*Plagionotus*) [unjustified emendation]

p. 244

printed:

arcuatus arcuatus Linnaeus, 1758: 399 (*Leptura*) E: AL AU BE BH BU BY CR CT CZ DE ?EN FI FR GE GR HU IR IT LA LT LU MC MD ME NL NR NT PL PT RO SB SK SL SP ST SV SZ TR UK N: AG MO TU A: GG IN KZ SY TR #64

apicalis Hampe, 1863: 289 (*Clytus*)

buyssoni Dauphin, 1924: 42

interruptecomatus Schmidt, 1951: 16

lunatus Fabricius, 1782: 500 (*Callidium*)

martialis Pic, 1918d: 15

milliati Pic, 1934e: 20

multiinterruptus Pic, 1933d: 6

pagnioni Pic, 1925d: 10

plavilstshikovi Schmidt, 1951: 15

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

reichei J. Thomson, 1861: 220 (*Plagyonotus*)

salicis Schrank, 1798: 677 (*Clytus*)

stauropolibus Pic, 1915e: 7

arcuatus ghidottii Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2011: 47 **E: GR**

arcuatus kirgizicus Lazarev, 2010c: 161 **A: KI**

arcuatus lugubris Ménériés, 1832: 229 (*Clytus*) **A: AB AR IN TM**

flavicornis Pic, 1898b: 19

henoni Pic, 1933d: 6

lenkoranus Pic, 1933d: 6

arcuatus multiinterruptus Pic, 1933: 6 **A: AB AR TR**

arcuatus tastani Özdikmen, Atak & Uçkan, 2017b: 89 **E: TR A: TR**

must be:

arcuatus arcuatus Linnaeus, 1758: 399 (*Leptura*) **E: AL AU BE BH BU BY CR CT
CZ DE ?EN FI FR GE GR HU IR IT LA LT LU MC MD ME NL NR NT PL PT
RO SB SK SL SP ST SV SZ TR UK N: AG MO TU A: GG IN KZ SY TR #64**

apicalis Hampe, 1863: 289 (*Clytus*)

buyssoni Dauphin, 1924: 42

interrupteconnatus Schmidt, 1951: 16

lunatus Fabricius, 1782: 500 (*Callidium*)

martialis Pic, 1918d: 15

milliati Pic, 1934e: 20

pagnioni Pic, 1925d: 10

plavilstshikovi Schmidt, 1951: 15

reichei J. Thomson, 1861: 220 (*Plagyonotus*)

salicis Schrank, 1798: 677 (*Clytus*)

stauropolibus Pic, 1915e: 7

arcuatus ghidottii Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2011: 47 **E: GR**

arcuatus kirgizicus Lazarev, 2010c: 161 **A: KI**

arcuatus lugubris Ménériés, 1832: 229 (*Clytus*) **A: AB ~~AR~~ IN TM**

flavicornis Pic, 1898b: 19

henoni Pic, 1933d: 6

lenkoranus Pic, 1933d: 6

arcuatus multiinterruptus Pic, 1933d: 6 **A: AB AR TR**

arcuatus tastani Özdikmen, Atak & Uçkan, 2017b: 89 **E: TR A: TR**

p. 249

printed:

genus *Teratoclytus* Zaitzev, 1937: 213 type species *Teratoclytus plavilstshikovi*
Zaitzev, 1937

changi Hayashi, 1983: 38 **A: TAI**

plavilstshikovi Zaitzev, 1937: 213 **A: FE JA ?NC NE SC SHX**

must be:

genus *Teratoclytus* D.W. Zaitzev, 1937: 213 type species *Teratoclytus*
plavilstshikovi D.W. Zaitzev, 1937

changi Hayashi, 1983: 38 **A: TAI**

plavilstshikovi D.W. Zaitzev, 1937: 213 **A: FE JA ?NC NE SC SHX**

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 250

A series of *Xylotrechus ilamensis* Holzschuh, 1979a was collected by A.Zubov in Russia (Dagestan in 2021). The taxon is preliminary identified as *X. i. zuvandiensis* Lazarev, 2016d.

pp.: 255, 274, 299, 330, 331, 333, 334, 359, 376, 387, 388, 390, 401, 415, 449, 465

printed:

Thomson

must be:

J. Thomson

p. 255

printed:

tristisfacies Sh. Yang & W. Yang, 2017: 82 **A: GUI**

must be:

tristisfacies Sh. Yang & W. Yang, 2017: 82 **A: GUI**

p. 255

printed:

aurescens Gressitt & Rondon, 1970: 186 **A: YUN ORR** #400

avarus Holzschuh, 1989a: 165 **A: HUN YUN ORR** #400

aurescens Gressitt & Rondon, 1970: 186 **A: YUN ORR** #289

auricomus Holzschuh, 1982a: 70 **A: NP**

must be:

aurescens Gressitt & Rondon, 1970: 186 **A: YUN ORR** #289 #400

auricomus Holzschuh, 1982a: 70 **A: NP**

avarus Holzschuh, 1989a: 165 **A: HUN YUN ORR** #400

p. 258

Axinopalpis gracilis (Krynicky, 1832) is absent in Lithuania and Latvia (according to V. Tamutis & D. Telnov, personal communications).

p. 259

printed:

fasciata Stephens, 1831: 250 (*Callidium*) **E: AL BH BU CR FR GR IT MA MC ME PT SB SL SP ST TR UK N: AG LB MO TU A: AB AR CY GG IN IS SY TR**

bipunctata Zubkov, 1833: 336 (*Callidium*)

brunnea Tournier, 1872: 280 (*Exilia*)

eggeri Adlbauer, 2006: 381 (*Graecoeme*)

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

fagnezi Pic, 1945b: 6

fasciolata Krynicky, 1834: 170 (*Callidium*)

lugubris Ragusa, 1884: 333 (*Exilia*)

timida Menetries, 1832: 228 (*Callidium*)

must be:

fasciata Stephens, 1831: 250 (*Callidium*) **E:** AL BH BU CR FR GR IT MA MC ME
PT SB SL SP ST TR UK **N:** AG LB MO TU **A:** AB AR CY GG IN IS SY TR **NTRI**

bipunctata Zubkov, 1833: 336 (*Callidium*)

brunnea Tournier, 1872: 280 (*Exilia*)

champlaini Knull, 1941: 695 (*Tylonotus*)

eggeri Adlbauer, 2006: 381 (*Graecoeme*)

fagnezi Pic, 1945b: 6

fasciolata Krynicky, 1834: 170 (*Callidium*)

lugubris Ragusa, 1884: 333 (*Exilia*)

timida Menetries, 1832: 228 (*Callidium*)

p. 261

printed:

platyfemur Chevrolat, 1882: 57 (*Hesperophanes*)

must be:

platifemur Chevrolat, 1882: 57 (*Hesperophanes*)

p. 261

Stromatium laticolle Pascoe, 1869a: 532 - a synonym of *Stromatium longicorne* (Newman, 1842) was missing.

p. 262

According to G. Tavakilian, it seems by the size and original description: *Hesperophanes tomentosus* Lucas, 1842 is a synonym of *Trichoferus griseus* (Fabricius, 1793) and not *Trichoferus fasciculatus fasciculatus* Faldermann, 1837 as it was accepted by Sama & Löbl (2010).

p. 262

Trichoferus pallidus (Olivier, 1790) was recorded for Turkey (Isparta) by Sama et al. (2011).

Trichoferus spartii (G. Müller, 1948) was recorded for Turkey (İzmir and Manisa) by Tezcan & Rejzek (2002) and by Tezcan & Can (2009).

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 265

printed:

ceramboides DeGeer, 1775: 151 (*Necydalis*)

must be:

ceramboides Forster, 1771: 47 (*Necydalis*)

p. 267

printed:

shibatai *okinawana* Hayashi & Matsuda, 1976: 34 A: JA (Ryukyus)

must be:

shibatai *okinawanus* Hayashi & Matsuda, 1976: 34 A: JA (Ryukyus)

p. 267

printed:

takeuchii ebenina Hayashi, 1961b: 45 A: JA (Ryukyus)

must be:

takeuchii ebeninus Hayashi, 1961 b: 45 A: JA (Ryukyus)

p. 271

printed:

fuscata Chevrolat, 1856c: 570 (*Obrium*) N: EG MO A: YE AFR

crinita Fähræus, 1872a: 55

must be:

fuscata Chevrolat, 1856c: 570 (*Obrium*) N: EG MO A: YE AFR

crinita Fähræus, 1872a: 55 (*Adiaphorus*)

senegalense J. Thomson, 1878a: 24 (*Obriacum*)

rubra Quentin, 1956: 41

See: Adlbauer & Beck (2015).

p. 280

Purpuricenus dalmatinus Sturm, 1843 was recorded from Egypt by Heyrovský (1951b).

p. 282

printed:

spectabilis Motschulsky, 1858a: 36 A: FUJ GAN GUI HEB HUB HUN JA JIA JIX

LIA SC SCH SHA ?TAI YUN ZHE #63 #185

bijunctus Pic, 1923b: 8 (*Stemoplites*)

must be:

spectabilis Motschulsky, 1858a: 36 A: FUJ GAN GUI HEB HUB HUN JA JIA JIX

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

LIA SC SCH SHA ?TAI YUN ZHE #63 #185

argodi Pic, 1949b: 53 (*Sternoplistes*)

bijunctus Pic, 1923b: 8 (*Sternoplistes*)

p. 282

According to Ambrus R. & Tichý T. (2020): *Purpuricenus malaccensis* (Lacordaire, 1869) = *P. diversithorax* Pic, 1922b = *P. d. v. subimmaculatus* Pic, 1927b

p. 283

A tribe was missing:

tribe Smodicini Lacordaire, 1869

genus Smodicum Haldeman, 1847: 38 type species *Callidium cucujiforme* Say, 1827

Nothorhinomorpha Pic, 1930e: 62 type species *Nothorhinomorpha deplanata* Pic, 1930e
cucujiforme Say, 1827: 277 (*Callidium*) **Ni: EG NAR NTR**

argentinum Bruch, 1911: 170

convergens Casey, 1912: 269

cylindrides Newman, 1838a: 394 (*Callidium*)

deplanata Pic, 1930e: 63 (*Nothorhinomorpha*) [Egypt]

According to Sama (2008b), *Callidium cucujiforme* Say, 1826 = *Nothorhinomorpha deplanata* Pic, 1930 described from Egypt.

p. 286

Callimus (Procallimus) semicyaneus Pic, 1905k was recorded for Turkey (Antalya: Alanya) by Adlbauer (1988) as *C. egregius semycianus*. It was also recorded for Turkey (Ankara, Icel) by Özdikmen (2021c: 817).

p. 291

printed:

dispar Fahraeus, 1872a: 49 **A: AE SA AFR**

must be:

dispar Fahraeus, 1872a: 49 **A: AE SA AFR**

curticollis Fairmaire, 1882b: 96

nitidiventris Fairmaire, 1887b: 326

parvicollis Fairmaire, 1892a: 120

See: Adlbauer & Beck (2015).

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 291

printed:

montanus Audinet-Serville, 1835a: 33

must be:

montanus Audinet-Serville, 1835a: 33 (*Aedilis*)

p. 292

printed:

elegans Ganglbauer, 1884: 534 A: AB IN

must be:

elegans Ganglbauer, 1884: 534 **E: ST** A: AB IN

Acanthocinus elegans Ganglbauer, 1884 was recorded for Dagestan (Samur delta, 30 km southwards Derbent) by Miroshnikov (2009a).

Miroshnikov A. I. 2009. K poznaniyu zhukov-drovosekov Kavkaza (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). 6. Zamechaniya o rasprostraneniі nekotorykh vidov s novymi dannymi po ikh biologii. - Entomologicheskoe obozrenie, 88 (4): 787-796.

p. 293

printed:

genus *Cristosydonia* Breuning, 1963b: 45 type species *Cristosydonia cristipennis* Breuning, 1963

alterna Holzschuh, 2003b: 312 A: NP SD

must be:

genus *Cristerysamena* Breuning, 1963b: 45 type species *Eyssamena cristipennis* Breuning, 1963

Cristosydonia Breuning, 1963b: 45 type species *Cristosydonia cristipennis* Breuning, 1963

alterna Holzschuh, 2003b: 312 (*Cristosydonia*) A: NP SD

besucheti Breuning, 1972c: 417 (*Eryssamena*) A: AP

p. 294

printed:

linnei Wallin, Nylander & Kvamme, 2009: 39 **E: AL AU BU BY CR CT CZ DE EN FR GB GE ?GR ?HU KZ LA LT MC MD ?ME NR ?NT PL ?PT RO ?SB SK ?SP ST SV SZ UK A: KZ WS #11 #64 #115 #479**

and

nebulosus nebulosus Linnaeus, 1758: 391 (*Cerambyx*) **E: ?AL ?AU BE BH BU ?CR CT(Kaliningrad) DE EN FI FR GB GE ?GR ?HU IR IT LA LS LU ?MD ?ME NL NR PL ?PT RO ?SB SL ?SP SV SZ TR UK A: ?KZ**

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

bifasciatus Goeze, 1777: 464 (*Cerambyx*) [hn]
dissimilis Pic, 1889a: 5
fasciatus Villers, 1789: 239 (*Cerambyx*) [hn]
monilis Geoffroy, 1785: 75 (*Cerambyx*)
siculus Pic, 1924c: 22 (*Liopus*)
taeniatus Gmelin, 1790: 1863 (*Cerambyx*)
unifasciatus Pic, 1891c: 23 (*Liopus*)

must be:

nebulosus nebulosus Linnaeus, 1758: 391 (*Cerambyx*) **E:** ?AL ?AU BE BH
BU ?CR CT(Kaliningrad) DE EN FI FR GB GE ?GR ?HU IR IT LA LS
LU ?MD ?ME NL NR PL ?PT RO ?SB SL ?SP SV SZ TR UK **A:** ?KZ

bifasciatus Goeze, 1777: 464 (*Cerambyx*) [hn]
dissimilis Pic, 1889a: 5
fasciatus Villers, 1789: 239 (*Cerambyx*) [hn]
monilis Geoffroy, 1785: 75 (*Cerambyx*)
siculus Pic, 1924c: 22 (*Liopus*)
unifasciatus Pic, 1891c: 23 (*Liopus*)

and

taeniatus Gmelin, 1790: 1863 (*Cerambyx*) **E:** AL AU BU BY CR CT CZ
DE EN FR GB GE ?GR ?HU KZ LA LT MC MD ?ME NR ?NT PL ?PT
RO ?SB SK ?SP ST SV SZ UK **A:** KZ WS #11 #64 #115 #479
linnei Wallin, Nylander & Kvamme, 2009: 39, **syn. nov.**

The name *Cerambyx taeniatus* Gmelin, 1790: 1863 (“Habitat in Sibiriae petrarum fissuris”) was based on the publication by Lepechin (1775: fig. 32), who really collected beetles in the West Siberia. But *L. nebulosus* absent in Siberia, where *L. linnei* is represented. So, *L. linnei* was described long ago as *Cerambyx taeniatus* Gmelin, 1790. *Cerambyx taeniatus* Gmelin, 1790 = *Leiopus linnei* Wallin, Nylander & Kvamme, 2009, **syn. nov.**

pp. 299-300

printed (p. 299):

genus *Aegomorphus* Haldeman, 1847: 45 type species *Aegomorphus decipiens*
Haldeman, 1847 (= *Lamia modesta* Gyllenhal, 1817)

and (p. 300)

genus *Psapharochrus* J. Thomson, 1864: 18 type species *Acanthoderes cylindricus*
Bates, 1861

jaspideus Germar, 1823: 475 (*Lamia*) **Ei:** AZ **NTR**

must be:

genus *Aegomorphus* Haldeman, 1847: 45 type species *Aegomorphus decipiens*
Haldeman, 1847 (= *Lamia modesta* Gyllenhal, 1817)

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

Psapharochrus J. Thomson, 1864: 18 type species *Acanthoderes cylindricus* Bates, 1861
Aethiopoctines Thomson, 1868c: 147 type species *Aethiopoctines leucogenus* Thomson,
1868c (= *Acanthoderes morrissi* Uhler, 1855)

...

jaspideus Germar, 1823: 475 (*Lamia*) Ei: AZ NTR
congener Blanchard, 1939: 183

p. 302

printed:

dahli dahli C.F.W. Richter, 1821: pl. 12 (*Saperda*) E: AL AU BE BH BU BY CR CT CZ
FR GE GR HU KZ MC MD ME RO SB SK SL SL SP ST ?SZ UK A: GG KZ #115

must be:

dahli dahli C.F.W. Richter, 1820: pl. 12 (*Saperda*) E: AL AU BE BH BU BY CR CT CZ
FR GE GR HU KZ MC MD ME RO SB SK SL SP ST ?SZ UK A: GG KZ #115

Agapanthia dahli (Richter, 1820) is the generally accepted date of original description (Bousquet, 2016). Though *Agapanthia dahli* (Richter, 1821) was published by Aurivillius (1923), Winkler (1929), Bense (1995), Sama (2002), Sama, Seddighi & Talebi (2008), Sama (2011), Sama & Rapuzzi (2012) and others.

p. 302

printed:

lateralis Ganglbauer, 1884: 541 E: TR

must be:

lateralis Ganglbauer, 1884: 541 E: TR A: TR

p. 303

The record of *Agapanthia maculicornis* for Turkey (Hakkari) by Fuchs & Breuning (1971) was connected with *A. fallax* (see Holzschuh, 1980). The record by Özdikmen & Okutaner (2006) for Kahramanmaraş could also be connected with a local taxon, but the record by Varlı et al. (2019) for Balıkesir could be exact. According to Özdikmen (2013): “old records from Turkey should be accept as wrong identifications”.

p. 304

Agapanthia amitina was recorded by Adlbauer (1992) for Turkey (Osmaniye and Icel: Çamliyayla) on the base of determination by G. Sama.

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

pp. 304-305

printed:

kirbyi kirbyi Gyllenhal, 1817: 186 (*Saperda*) E: AL BH BU CR CT FR GR HU IT IQ KZ MD ME RO SB SK SP ST TR UK A: AB AR GG IN IS SY TM TR

latipennis Mulsant, 1862: 352

zawadskyi Fairmaire, 1866b: 275

kirbyi valandovensis Sláma, 2015c: 1127 E: MC

must be:

kirbyi kirbyi Gyllenhal, 1817: 186 (*Saperda*) E: BU_CT FR HU IT KZ MD RO SK SP ST TR UK

latipennis Mulsant, 1862: 352

kirbyi zawadskyi Fairmaire, 1866b: 275 E: AL BH BU CR GR MC ME SB A: AR AB IN IQ TM TR

valandovensis Sláma, 2015c: 1127 E: MC

Agapanthia kirbyi (Gyllenhal, 1817) from Tanscaucasia and Balkans is just same as from Macedonia described as *A. kirbyi valandovensis* Sláma, 2015c. Populations from Armenia, Azerbaijan, Iran, Iraq, Turkmenistan, Near East and Balkans could be identified as *A. kirbyi zawadskyi* Fairmaire, 1866b: 275 [“Kisilgye-Aole” (?Kizilkaya, Burdur prov.), “aussi à Constantinople”] (= *A. kirbyi valandovensis* Sláma, 2015c, **syn. nov.**).

p. 305

printed:

pachypezoides J. Thomson, 1864: 99 A: FUJ GUA GUI HUB HUN JA JIA JIX SCH TAI ZHE

breviscapus Heller, 1923b: 73 (*Phelipara*)

must be:

pachypezoides J. Thomson, 1864: 99 A: FUJ GUA GUI HUB HUN JA JIA JIX SCH TAI ZHE

breviscapus Heller, 1923b: 73 (*Phelipara*)

p. 306

printed:

mniszecchi Lacordaire, 1872: 696 (*Smermus*) A: NP SD

rufovittatus Breuning, 1966a: 109

must be:

mniszecchi Lacordaire, 1872: 696 (*Smermus*) A: NP SD

aureomaculata Hüdepohl, 1990: 454 (*Antennopothyne*)

rufovittatus Breuning, 1966a: 109

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

According to Hüddepohl (1995), *Smermus mniszzechi* Lacordaire, 1872 = *Antennopothyne aureomaculata* Hüddepohl, 1990.

p. 306

printed:

genus *Coreocalamobius* Hasegawa, Han & Oh, 2014: 50 type species *Coreocalamobius parantennatus* Hasegawa, Han & Oh, 2014
parantennatus Hasegawa, Han & Oh, 2014: 50 A: ?JA (Tsushima Is.) SC
must be:

genus *Coreocalamobius* Hasegawa, Han & Oh, 2014: 50 type species *Coreocalamobius parantennatus* Hasegawa, Han & Oh, 2014
parantennatus Hasegawa, Han & Oh, 2014: 50 A: SC

According to N. Ohbayashi (personal message, 11.5.2022), the record of *Theophilea cylindricollis* for Tsushima Is. was connected with misidentification of *Pseudocalamobius tsushimae*, but not *Coreocalamobius parantennatus*, as it was supposed by Danilevsky (2020: 12) in the Catalogue.

p. 310

Theophilea subcylindricollis was recorded for Turkey (Izmir) by Pesarini & Sabbadini (2004b).

p. 310

printed:

genus *Trichopothyne* Breuning, 1942a: 168 type species *Trichopothyne strandiella* Breuning, 1942
hindostanica Breuning, 1950d: 258 A: UP

must be:

genus *Trichopothyne* Breuning, 1942a: 168 type species *Trichopothyne strandiella* Breuning, 1942
hindostani Breuning, 1950d: 258 A: UP

p. 310

printed:

genus *Idactus* Pascoe, 1864c: 273 type species *Idactus tridens* Pascoe, 1864
Togonius Kolbe, 1893: 64 type species *Togonius klingi* Kolbe, 1893

must be:

genus *Idactus* Pascoe, 1864c: 273 type species *Idactus tridens* Pascoe, 1864
Pseudocrossotus Breuning, 1978d: 897 type species *Pseudocrossotus enricoi* Breuning, 1978

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

(= *Idactus ashanticus* Breuning, 1960)

Togonius Kolbe, 1893: 64 type species *Togonius klingi* Kolbe, 1893

p. 310

printed:

coquereli Fairmaire, 1890: 551 (*Dichostates*) A: AE IN OM YE AFR
iranicus Breuning, 1975d: 348 #342

must be:

coquereli Fairmaire, 1890: 551 (*Dichostates*) A: AE IN OM YE AFR
iranicus Breuning, 1975d: 348 #342
variegatus Gestro, 1895: 425

p. 311

printed:

genus *Parorsidis* Breuning, 1935d: 65 type species *Parorsidis birmanica* Breuning, 1935

Paranephelotes Breuning, 1935e: 252 type species *Paranephelotes laosensis* Breuning, 1935

nigrosarsa nigrosarsa Pic, 1926a: 15 (*Ostedes*) A: BT GUA HAI ORR #400
birmanica Breuning, 1935d: 65

must be:

nigrosarsa nigrosarsa Pic, 1926a: 15 (*Driopea*) A: BT GUA HAI ORR #400
birmanica Breuning, 1935d: 65
fouqueti Pic, 1936a: 19 (*Ostedes*)
laosensis Breuning, 1935e: 252 (*Paranephelotes*)

p. 312

printed:

pulchra nitidipennis Holzschuh, 2019a: 72 A: SHA

must be:

pulchra nitidiceps Holzschuh, 2019a: 72 A: SHA

p. 314

printed:

granulatus Jongok Lim, 2013: 359 A: JAi SC

must be:

granulata Jongok Lim, 2013: 359 A: JAi SC

p. 314

printed:

genus *Eupogonius* LeConte, 1852: 159 type species *Desmiphora tomentosa* Haldeman, 1847

Eriopsilus Bates, 1866b: 193 type species *Eriopsilus nigrinus* Bates, 1866

Phydola J. Thomson, 1864: 110 type species *Phydola maculicornis* Chevrolat, 1862

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

tomentosus Haldeman, 1847: 50 (*Desmiphora*) Ni: MO NAR
pinivorus Fitch, 1859: 712

According to #486, the genus must be deleted from the Catalogue (no species in Palaearctic Region). Besides, the correct spelling is “*Phidola*” originally proposed by Dejean (1835) as unavailable and became available as *Phidola* Chevrolat, 1862: 254.

Chevrolat L. A. A. 1862. Coléoptères de l'Île de Cuba. Notes, synonymies et descriptions d'espèces nouvelles. Familles des Cérambycides et des Parandrides. - Annales de la Société Entomologique de France, (4) 2: 245-280.

p. 317

printed:

latefasciata Breuning, 1958c: 36 A: BT

must be:

latefasciatus Breuning, 1958c: 36 A: BT

p. 321

printed:

genus *Apomecyna* Dejean, 1821: 108 type species type species *Saperda alboguttata* Megerle, 1802 (= *Lamia histrio* Fabricius, 1793)

Anapomecyna Pic, 1925a: 29 type species *Anapomecyna luteomaculata* Pic, 1925

Crassapomecyna Breuning, 1958i: 492 type species *Apomecyna crassiuscula* Fairmaire, 1896

Mecynapus J. Thomson, 1858: 187 type species *Apomecyna parumpunctata* Chevrolat, 1856

Pseudoalbana Pic, 1895c: 77 type species *Pseudoalbana lameerei* Pic, 1895

Vocula Lacordaire, 1872: 587 type species *Vocula irrorata* Lacordaire, 1872
(= *Apomecyna parumpunctata* Chevrolat, 1856)

must be:

genus *Apomecyna* Dejean, 1821: 108 type species *Saperda alboguttata* Megerle, 1802 (= *Lamia histrio* Fabricius, 1793)

Anapomecyna Pic, 1925a: 29 type species *Anapomecyna luteomaculata* Pic, 1925

Crassapomecyna Breuning, 1958i: 492 type species *Apomecyna crassiuscula* Fairmaire, 1896

Mecynapus J. Thomson, 1858: 187 type species *Apomecyna parumpunctata* Chevrolat, 1856

Parapomecyna Breuning, 1968g: 345 type species *Parapomecyna flavomaculata* Breuning, 1968 (= *Apomecyna quadrisignata* Quedenfeldt, 1885)

Pseudoalbana Pic, 1895c: 77 type species *Pseudoalbana lameerei* Pic, 1895

Vocula Lacordaire, 1872: 587 type species *Vocula irrorata* Lacordaire, 1872
(= *Apomecyna parumpunctata* Chevrolat, 1856)

p. 327

printed:

lineatithorax Pic, 1927b: 17 A: NP ORR

elongata Pic, 1929a: 30 (*Sybra*)

vietnamensis Breuning, 1972b: 235

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

must be:

lineatithorax Pic, 1927b: 17 A: NP ORR

curtelineata Pic, 1945a: 3

elongata Pic, 1929a: 30 (*Sybra*)

griseosparsa Pic, 1927c: 17

vietnamensis Breuning, 1972b: 235

p. 328

printed:

alternans Wiedemann, 1823: 11 (*Lamia*) A: ?TAI NTRi ORR #219 #400

angustata Pic, 1926b: 6 (*Atelais*)

carolina Matsushita, 1935: 121

fuscovittata Aurivillius, 1927: 24

latiuscula Aurivillius, 1927: 23

must be:

alternans Wiedemann, 1823: 11 (*Lamia*) A: ?TAI NTRi ORR #219 #400

angustata Pic, 1926b: 6 (*Atelais*)

carolina Matsushita, 1935: 121

fuscovittata Aurivillius, 1927: 24

javaensis Breuning, 1982a: 10 (*Falsoropica*)

ochreovittata Breuning, 1939a: 77

According to Weigel & Skale (2016, 2017), *Sybra latiuscula* Aurivillius, 1927 is a valid name of a species from Philippines.

p. 328

printed:

icanoides Breuning, 1942a: 150 A: SD

must be:

arator Pascoe, 1865a: 210 A: SD ORR

icanoides Breuning, 1942a: 150

See: Skale & Weigel (2014).

p. 328

printed:

mimogeminata Breuning & K. Ohbayashi, 1964: 17 A: JA (Ryukyus)

carinatipennis Breuning & Chûjô, 1970: 56

musashinoi Breuning & Chûjô, 1970: 56

must be:

mimogeminata Breuning & K. Ohbayashi, 1964: 17 A: JA (Ryukyus)

carinatipennis Breuning & Chûjô, 1970: 56

miyakoana Hayashi, 1972: 31

musashinoi Breuning & Chûjô, 1970: 56

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 329

printed:

sikkimensis Breuning, 1939b: 270 A: SD

must be:

leucostictica Breuning, 1939b: 266 A: SD ORR

ochraceicollis Breuning, 1940: 162

pulvereoides Breuning, 1939: 268

sikkimensis Breuning, 1939b: 270

See: Weigel & Skale (2011).

p. 333-334

printed:

kuntzeni Kriesche, 1915: 139

as a synonym of *Batocera horsfieldii* Hope, 1839 (p. 333)

and

as a synonym of *Batocera rufomaculata rufomaculata* (DeGeer, 1775)
(p. 334)

First case was wrong.

p. 334

printed:

downesii Hope, 1845b: 76

as a synonym of *Batocera roylii* (Hope, 1833)

and

as a synonym of *Batocera rubus rubus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

First case was wrong.

p. 335

printed:

aestuans Olivier, 1800: 123 (*Cerambyx*) N: MO AFR #373

aegyptiaca Gilmour, 1956c: 753

senegalensis Fiedler, 1938: 591

must be:

aestuans Olivier, 1800: 123 (*Cerambyx*) N: MO AFR #373

aegyptiaca Gilmour, 1956c: 753

dakarensis Fiedler, 1938: 591

guineensis Hintz, 1920: 165

nigerica Fiedler, 1938: 592

ornata Hintz, 1920: 165

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

senegalensis Fiedler, 1938: 591

ubangiensis Fiedler, 1938: 592

p. 335

printed:

wallichi wallichi Hope, 1831: 27 (*Lamia*) A: AP GUI HP NP PA SD SCH UP YUN

ORR #368 #369

tricincta Duncan, 1835: 254 (*Lamia*)

must be:

wallichi wallichi Hope, 1831: 27 (*Lamia*) A: AP GUI HP NP PA SD SCH UP YUN

ORR #368 #369

insularis Fisher, 1935: 609 (*Diastocera*)

tricincta Duncan, 1835: 254 (*Lamia*)

trivittata Gistel & Bromme, 1850: 624 (*Ceroplesis*)

p. 335

printed:

subocellatus heimschi Peyerimhoff, 1923b: 318 N: AG MO

subocellatus subocellatus Fairmaire, 1886a: 458 (*Dichosthates*) N: AG EG LB SI

AFR

phillippsi Gahan, 1896: 458

must be:

subocellatus Fairmaire, 1886a: 458 (*Dichosthates*) N: AG EG LB MO SI **AFR**

heimschi Peyerimhoff, 1923b: 318

phillippsi Gahan, 1896: 458

p. 335-336

printed:

tubericollis Fairmaire, 1891: 271 (*Dichosthates*) N: MO **AFR**

robustus Jordan, 1894a: 236

vittatus Aurivillius, 1914: 30

must be:

tubericollis Fairmaire, 1891: 271 (*Dichosthates*) N: MO **AFR**

bimaculatus Aurivillius, 1903: 323

robustus Jordan, 1894a: 236

vittatus Aurivillius, 1914: 30

p. 335-336

printed (p. 336):

saudicola Teocchi, 1991: 304

must be (p. 335):

erlangeri erlangeri Hintz, 1912: 195 **AFR**

erlangeri saudicola Teocchi, 1991: 304 A: SA

p. 336

printed:

vagepictus Fairmaire, 1886a: 456 **A: SA AFR**
adenensis Breuning, 1969f: 665
lateralis Hintz, 1912: 194
obliquevittatus Breuning, 1940c: 166
saudicola Teocchi, 1991: 304

must be:

vagepictus Fairmaire, 1886a: 456 **A: SA AFR**
adenensis Breuning, 1969f: 665
niveicollis Hintz, 1912: 194
lateralis Hintz, 1912: 194
obliquevittatus Breuning, 1940c: 166

p. 336

printed:

verrucicollis Gahan, 1894a: 60 **A: NP ORR**

must be:

verrucicollis Gahan, 1894a: 60 (*Moechotypa*) **A: NP ORR**

p. 336

printed:

favosum J. Thomson, 1864: 48 **A: YE AFR**

must be:

favosa J. Thomson, 1864: 48 **A: YE AFR**

pp. 337-338

printed:

mystacinum mystacinum Ballion, 1878: 369 **A: KI KZ ?UZ**
ataense Pic, 1901e: 18
auliense Pic, 1901p: 69
capreolum Heyden, 1887d: 317
kusnezovi Jakovlev, 1906b: 40

mystacinum pumilio Plavilstshikov, 1951: 114 **A: KZ**

mystacinum rufidens Jakovlev, 1906b: 39 **A: KZ**

must be:

kusnezovi kusnezovi Jakovlev, 1906b: 40 **A: KI KZ ?UZ**

[*ataense* Pic, 1901e: 18] - unavailable name

[*auliense* Pic, 1901p: 69] - unavailable name

[*capreolum* Heyden, 1887b: 317] - unavailable name

kusnezovi pumilio Plavilstshikov, 1951: 114 **A: KZ**

kusnezovi rufidens Jakovlev, 1906b: 39 **A: KZ**

...

mystacinum Ballion, 1878: 369 **A: XIN**

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

Traditional interpretation of *Dorcadion mystacinum* Ballion, 1878, as a species from Kazakhstan and Kirgizia was wrong (beginning from Heyden, 1887b: 316 - "Alexander-Gebirg"). It was described from "Kuldsha", but many of consequent authors ignored that record. Plavilstshikov (1958: 381) declared the records from Kuldzha as incorrect. According to Danilevsky (2012i), "The original geographical record is generally accepted as wrong".

Recently M. Danilevsky received from Lin Mei-Ying photos of two *Dorcadion* males from Xinjiang for determination. Both are very similar to the species from Kazakhstan and Kirgizia traditionally identified as *D. mystacinum*, and both are real *D. mystacinum*, described by Ballion from Kuldzha. So, real *D. mystacinum* Ballion is known up to now from Xinjiang only and absent in Kazakhstan and Kirgizia.

Similar species from Kazakhstan and Kirgizia needs another name.

Dorcadion mystacinum var. *capreolus* Heyden, 1887b ("Alexander Gebirg") must be regarded as unavailable, as "its author expressly gave it intrasubspecific rank" according to the Article 45.6.4. of ICZN. It was based on a female from a series of typical form.

Dorcadion mystacinum var. *ataense* Pic, 1901e: 18 ["Aulie-Ata"] and *D. mystacinum* var. *auliense* Pic, 1901p: 69 ["Turk."] are both also unavailable, as two variations from one population.

The valid name is *D. kusnezovi* Jakovlev, 1906b. The species was described from Aulie-Ata (Dzhambul = Taraz).

p. 338

printed:

optatum kadyrbekovi Danilevsky, 1999b: 20 A: KZ

must be:

optatum kadyrbekovi Danilevsky, 1999b: 20 A: KI

p. 339

Several Albanian local forms of *Dorcadion aethiops* are regarded as subspecies: *D. a. balthasari* Heyrovský, 1962 (Shkodër, Tirana, Sauk); *D. a. laevepunctatum* Breuning, 1944 (Mali i Thate); *D. a. maderi* Breit, 1923 (Vora, Kruja, Elbasan); *D. a. sterbai* Breuning, 1944 (Moskopolje = Voskopoje, Kulmak), **stat. nov.**

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 341

printed:

berytense breuning, 1964c: 31 (Beiruth)

must be:

berytense Breuning, 1964c: 31 (Beiruth)

p. 342

printed:

mancum Gistel, 1848: 431

must be:

mancum Gistel, 1850: 431

p. 344

printed:

subfurcatum Pic, 1914b: 9

must be:

subfurcatum Pic, 1913b: 129

p. 345

printed:

elegans Kraatz, 1873a: 73 **E: KZ ST UK A: KZ**

must be:

elegans Kraatz, 1873a: 73 **E: KZ ST UK A: KZ WS**

The species is known from Kurgan region of Russia.

p. 345

printed:

equestre equestre Laxmann, 1770: 596 (*Cerambyx*) **E: CT ST UK A: ?GG (?Gagry)**

must be:

equestre equestre Laxmann, 1770: 596 (*Cerambyx*) **E: CT ST UK A: ?GG (?Gagry) KZ**

Dorcadion equestre was recorded for north-east Kazakhstan by Bragina & Maruarova (2016) - Naurzum Natural Reserve in Kustanay Region.

p. 345

printed:

subcostatum Heyden, 1887d: 323

must be:

subcostatum Heyden, 1887b: 323

p. 346

printed:

glaucum lassalei Lazarev, 2015: 1112 A: IN

must be:

glaucum lassalei Lazarev, 2015: 1112 A: IN

p. 349

printed:

kurdistanum Breuning, 1944a: 12 A: TR

must be:

kurdistanum kurdistanum Breuning, 1944a: 12 [“Kourdistan: Diarbékir”] A: TR

kurdistanum rufulipes Breuning, 1971c: 437 [“nö Bingol”] A: TR

Dorcadion kurdistanum m. *rufulipes* Breuning, 1963f was described from “Kudistan: Meleto Dagh” [north of Batman prov.] on the base of a single male with red legs. The name was validated as *D. k. rufulipes* Breuning in Fuchs & Breuning (1971) from “nö Bingol 1600-1900 m”. *D. kurdistanum* Breuning, 1944a was described from “Kourdistan: Diarbékir” on the base of a single male with black legs.

p. 357

A female of *Dorcadion serouense* Kadlec, 2006b from Iraq (Penjwin or Banjwin, 1300 m, 13.5.1976 J. Macek leg.) is preserved in S. Murzin collection (Moscow) - new geographical record.

p. 357

printed:

dsungaricum Pic, 1907d: 104

must be:

dsungaricum Pic, 1907b: 11

p. 370

printed:

fuliginator fuliginator Linnaeus, 1758: 393 (*Cerambyx*) E: AU BE FR GE LA
LU NL SZ

must be:

fuliginator fuliginator Linnaeus, 1758: 393 (*Cerambyx*) E: AU BE FR GE LU
NL SZ

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

According to D. Telnov (personal message to M. Danilevsky, 25.03.2022) all records (Telnov et al., 1997; Sifverberg, 2004; Telnov, 2004; Dunskis & Barševskis, 2018) of *Iberodorcadion fuliginator* for Latvia were based on wrong data (one specimen from Kandava area, Central Latvia). In fact, no specimens were ever known.

p. 371

printed:

fallax Kraatz, 1873a: 89 (*Dorcadion*) E: BU GR MV

must be:

fallax Kraatz, 1873a: 89 (*Dorcadion*) E: BU GR

Wrong line was published before by Sama & Löbl (2010: 263). Most probably the misprint was connected with wrong spelling of “MC” - Macedonia, but we don’t have any data on the occurrence of *Neodorcadion fallax* in Macedonia. It is known from neighbor regions of Greece.

Neodorcadion fallax was recorded for European and Asian Turkey (İstanbul province) by Özdikmen (2021b: 1451) with the reference to Özdikmen (2021a: 785), where the species was recorded for Asian Turkey only. Both records were based on the old record by Breuning (1947e: 170) for “Alem Dagh” (Asian part of Istanbul) with new m. *rufobrunneum*. But later Breuning (1962a) did not repeat this record neither m. *rufobrunneum*. So, we have no evidence of the presence of *Neodorcadion fallax* in Turkey.

p. 375

printed:

arabica Breuning, 1968c: 90 A: SA YE

arabensis Breuning, 1969d: 104 [RN]

must be:

arabica Breuning, 1968c: 90 A: SA YE

arabensis Breuning, 1969d: 104 [unnecessary substitute name]

p. 375

printed:

laterita Fairmaire, 1903: 255 (*Diadelia*)

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

must be:

lateritia Fairmaire, 1903: 255 (*Diadelia*)

p. 376

printed:

yemenensis Breuning, 1968c: 90 A: YE

must be:

yemeniensis Breuning, 1968c: 90 A: YE

pp. 378-379

printed (p. 379):

seticollis Fisher, 1932: 300 A: UP

must be (p. 378):

fumosus Gahan, 1894a: 85-86 A: UP **ORR**

seticollis Fisher, 1932: 300

New synonyms *Exocentrus fumosus* Gahan, 1894 = *E. seticollis* Fisher, 1932 were published by Holzschuh (2015b) together with the records of the species for Myanmar, Laos, Vietnam. Though later (Kariyanna et al., 2017) *E. seticollis* Fisher, 1932 was published as valid once more.

p. 379

printed:

nobuoi okinawensis Breuning & K. Ohbayashi, 1966: 35 A: JA (Ryukyus)

paraguttulatus Breuning & Chûjô, 1971: 31 A: JA (Okinawa)

must be:

nobuoi okinawensis Breuning & K. Ohbayashi, 1966: 35 A: JA (Ryukyus)

paraguttulatus Breuning & Chûjô, 1971: 31

According to H. Makihara and M. Hasegawa (personal messages, 2021), *Exocentrus nobuoi okinawensis* Breuning & K. Ohbayashi, 1966 = *Ex. paraguttulatus* Breuning & Chûjô, 1971.

p. 380

printed:

binhanus Pic, 1926e: 48 (*Exocentrus*) A: HAI HKG **ORR**

laterimaculatus Gressitt, 1940b: 188

must be:

binhana Pic, 1926e: 48 (*Exocentrus*) A: HAI HKG **ORR**

laterimaculata Gressitt, 1940b: 188

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 381

printed:

genus *Trichognoma* Breuning, 1956g: 674 type species *Trichognoma chinense*
Breuning, 1956

chinense Breuning, 1956g: 674 A: HUB

must be:

genus *Trichognoma* Breuning, 1956g: 674 type species *Trichognoma chinense*
Breuning, 1956

chinensis Breuning, 1956g: 674 A: HUB

p. 383

printed:

fasciata Gestro, 1891: 222 A: GUX YUN **ORR**

grisea Pic, 1927b: 35

must be:

fasciata Gestro, 1891: 222 A: GUX YUN **ORR**

grisea Pic, 1927b: 35

laosica Breuning, 1965e: 46

The synonym was shown by Tavakilian (2021).

Tavakilian, G. (author) & Chevillotte, H. (software) 2021: *Titan: base de données internationales sur les Cerambycidae ou Longicornes*. Version [2021].
[<http://titan.gbif.fr>]

pp. 386, 416

printed:

lethalis J. Thomson, 1857e: 182 A: SCH YUN **ORR**

morimoides White, 1858a: 266 (*Leprodera*)

quadrimaculatus Pic, 1925a: 17 (*Trachystola*)

trinotatus Pic, 1925a: 17 (*Trachystola*)

whitei Lacordaire, 1869: 298

and (p. 416)

distincta Gahan, 1888d: 392 (*Monohamus*) A: NP SD YUN

quadrimaculata Pic, 1925a: 17 (*Trachystola*)

tonkinensis Pic, 1926g: 143 (*Nephelotes*)

trinotata Pic, 1925a: 17 (*Trachystola*)

First case is correct.

p. 388, 393

printed:

subgenus *Mesagelasta* Breuning, 1939c: 494 type species *Anagelasta trimaculata*
Breuning, 1938

nigromaculata Breuning, 1938c: 212 A: HP

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

must be (p. 393):

setulosa Breuning, 1938c: 202 A: HP NP

nigromaculata Breuning, 1938c: 212 (*Anagelasta*)

According to Weigel (2006: 503), *Mesosa setulosa* Breuning, 1938c = *Anagelasta nigromaculata* Breuning, 1938c.

p. 389

printed:

aedificator Fabricius, 1793: 275 (*Lamia*) A: AP KA OM PA SA ?TAI UP YE AFR

ORR #127 #274 #280

ambulator Fabricius, 1775: 171 (*Lamia*)

bidens Wollaston, 1877: 210

fuscus Olivier, 1797: 462 (*Lamia*) [1800: 83 (*Cerambyx*)] #373

parallelus Audinet-Serville, 1835a: 64

quadrisignatus Fähræus, 1872b: 30

villicus Olivier, 1797: 468 (*Lamia*) [1800: 102 (*Cerambyx*)]

must be:

aedificator Fabricius, 1793: 275 (*Lamia*) A: AP KA OM PA SA ?TAI UP YE AFR

ORR #127 #274 #280

ambulator Fabricius, 1775: 171 (*Lamia*)

bidens Wollaston, 1877: 210

fuscus Olivier, 1797: 462 (*Lamia*) [1800: 83 (*Cerambyx*)] #373

inhambanensis Bertoloni, 1876: 263 (*Phymasterna*)

parallelus Audinet-Serville, 1835a: 64

quadrisignatus Fähræus, 1872b: 30

villicus Olivier, 1797: 468 (*Lamia*) [1800: 102 (*Cerambyx*)]

p. 391

According to J. Yamasako and Lin Meiyang (personal messages, March 2020), the record of *Mesosa longipennis* Bates, 1873 for Sichuan by Lazarev & Murzin (2020) was based on misidentification of *Mesosa latifasciata* (White, 1858), as well as probably many other records of *Mesosa longipennis* for China. *M. longipennis* definitely known from Japan and South Korea. It could also occur in North China, but no Chinese specimens are known.

p. 391

printed:

latifasciata White, 1858b: 401 (*Cacia*) A: FUJ GAN GUA GUI GUX HAI HEB

JIA JIX SCH SHX TAI ZHE **ORR #60 #271 #489**

luteopubens Pic, 1917c: 7

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

must be:

latifasciata White, 1858b: 401 (*Cacia*) A: FUJ GAN GUA GUI GUX HAI HEB JIA
JIX SCH SHX TAI ZHE **ORR #60 #271 #489**

latifasciata Matsushita, 1931a: 44
luteopubens Pic, 1917c: 7

p. 394

printed:

genus *Pseudoclyzomedus* Yamasako, 2009: 282 type species *Pseudoclyzomedus*
ohbayashii Yamasako, 2009

hainanus Yamasako & Liu, 2019: 2 A: HAI

must be:

genus *Pseudoclyzomedus* Yamasako, 2009: 282 type species *Pseudoclyzomedus*
ohbayashii Yamasako, 2009

hainanus Yamasako & Liu, 2019: 370 A: HAI

p. 395, 397

printed:

(p. 395)

cervina Hope, 1831: 27 (*Monochamus*) A: AP FUJ GUA GUI GUX HAI HUB JIX
NP SCH SHA XIZ YUN ZHE **ORR #280**

fulvicornis Pascoe, 1875: 64 (*Monochamus*)

(p. 397)

sejuncta sejuncta Bates, 1873: 310 (*Monohammus*) A: FE (Sakhalin, Kunashir) FUJ
HUB JA NC SC

fraxini Matsushita, 1933a: 328 (*Dihammus*)

fulvicornis Pascoe, 1875: 64 (*Monochamus*)

olivacea Breuning, 1944b: 471 (*Dihammus*)

Second case is correct.

p. 398

printed:

rusticator rusticator Fabricius, 1801: 294 (*Lamia*) A: TAI **ORR**

bianor Newman, 1842b: 277 (*Monohammus*)

fistulatrix Germar, 1823: 478 (*Lamia*) **#506**

musiva Pascoe, 1866b: 251 (*Monochamus*)

must be:

rusticator rusticator Fabricius, 1801: 294 (*Lamia*) A: TAI **ORR**

bianor Newman, 1842b: 277 (*Monohammus*)

brunnescens Breuning, 1980: 175

fistulator Germar, 1823: 478 (*Lamia*) **#506**

musiva Pascoe, 1866b: 251 (*Monochamus*)

whiteheadi Breuning, 1970: 474

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

According to Vitali (2016a), *Lamia rusticator* Fabricius, 1801 = *Acalolepta whiteheadi* Breuning, 1970 = *Acalolepta brunnescens* Breuning, 1980.

p. 400

printed:

laevigatrix J. Thomson, 1857f: 297 (*Cerosterna*)

must be:

laevigator J. Thomson, 1857f: 297 (*Cerosterna*)

as it was published originally - Art. 31.2.1

p. 401

printed:

stanleyana Hope, 1839: 43 A: BT NP SD SE SW **ORR**

angustata Pic, 1934a: 11 [HN]

chapaensis Breuning, 1950i: 511

gloriosa Tippmann, 1953: 152

grisea Tippmann, 1953: 153

melancholica Tippmann, 1953: 153

tonkinea Breuning, 1943c: 285 [RN]

must be:

stanleyana Hope, 1839: 43 A: BT NP SD SE SW **ORR**

angustata Pic, 1934a: 11 [HN]

chapaensis Breuning, 1950i: 511

gloriosa Tippmann, 1953: 152

melancholica Tippmann, 1953: 153

tonkinea Breuning, 1943c: 285 [RN]

According to Lingafelter & Hoebeke (2002: 46-47), *Anoplophora birmanica* Hüdepohl, 1990 is the same species as *A. stanleyana* var. *grisea* Tippmann, 1953. But these authors accepted *grisea* Tippmann, 1953 as unavailable name without adequate reasons. So, the valid name of the species is *A. grisea* Tippmann, 1953 = *A. birmanica* Hüdepohl, 1990, **syn. nov.** distributed in Myanmar and Assam.

p. 402

printed:

stigmatosus Gahan, 1894a: 44 A: YUN **ORR**

laosicus Pic, 1930b: 18 (*Epepeotes*)

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

must be:

stigmatosus Gahan, 1894a: 44 **A: YUN ORR**

laosensis Pic, 1930b: 18 (*Epepeotes*)

p. 403

printed:

praetorius Erichson, 1834: 268 (*Lamia*) **A: TAI (Lanyu Is.) ORR**

shamankariyali Kano, 1939: 30

must be:

praetorius Erichson, 1834: 268 (*Lamia*) **A: TAI (Lanyu Is.) ORR**

elpenor Pascoe, 1862a: 344

shamankariyali Kano, 1939: 30

p. 403

printed:

scabratrix Fabricius, 1781: 224 (*Lamia*) **A: NP PA UP ORR**

gladiatrix Fabricius, 1801: 284 (*Lamia*)

griseatrix Aurivillius, 1920: 12 (*Celosterna*)

murina Nonfried, 1894: 82 (*Aristobia*)

renei Pascoe, 1888: 501 (*Psaromaia*)

spinatrix Fabricius, 1798: 145 (*Lamia*)

must be:

scabrator Fabricius, 1781: 224 (*Lamia*) **A: NP PA UP ORR**

gladiator Fabricius, 1801: 284 (*Lamia*)

griseator Aurivillius, 1920: 12 (*Celosterna*)

murina Nonfried, 1894: 82 (*Aristobia*)

renei Pascoe, 1888: 501 (*Psaromaia*)

spinator Fabricius, 1798: 145 (*Lamia*)

p. 404

printed:

tesselata White, 1858b: 404 (*Celosterna*)

must be:

tessellata White, 1858b: 404 (*Celosterna*)

p. 405

printed:

carcelli Guérin-Méneville, 1833b: 491 (*Lamia*)

must be:

carcelii Guérin-Méneville, 1833b: 491 (*Lamia*)

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 406

printed:

yaveyamensis Samuelson, 1965b: 96 A: JA (Ryukyus)

must be:

yaeyamensis Samuelson, 1965b: 96 A: JA (Ryukyus)

p. 408

printed:

hiekei Breuning, 1964g: 445 A: BT

(as *Monochamus*)

According to Weigel (2018), *Morimopsidius triangularis* Breuning, 1948 = *Monochamus hiekei* Breuning, 1964 - now in genus *Pseudhepomidion* Breuning, 1936.

p. 408

Monochamus kaszabi Heyrovský, 1955 was placed by Hayashi (1963a) in the subgenus *Opepharus* Pascoe, 1868.

p. 408

printed:

subfasciatus shikokensis Breuning, 1956a: 1 A: JA

must be:

subfasciatus shikokuensis Breuning, 1956a: 1 A: JA

p. 410

printed:

genus *Opepharus* Pascoe, 1868: xiii type species *Opepharus signator* Pascoe, 1868
(= *Monochamus tridentatus* Chevrolat, 1833)

Lophoptera Perroud, 1855: 352 [HN] type species *Lophoptera spectabilis* Perroud, 1855

Zephyropepharus Hayashi, 1962c: 6 type species *Opepharus asiaticus* Hayashi, 1962
asiaticus Hayashi, 1962: 7 A: JA (Ryukyus)

Opepharus Pascoe, 1868 must be accepted as a subgenus of *Monochamus* Dejean, 1821.

p. 410

printed:

officinatrix White, 1858b: 409 (*Monohammus*)

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

must be:

officator White, 1858b: 409 (*Monohammus*)

p. 412

printed:

antennata Gahan, 1894a: 46 A: FUJ GUX SD YUN **ORR**

tuberculifera Pic, 1903b: 22 (*Triammatus*)

must be:

antennata Gahan, 1894a: 46 A: FUJ GUX SCH SD YUN **ORR**

rondoni Breuning, 1963d: 20

tuberculifera Pic, 1903b: 22 (*Triammatus*)

p. 413

printed:

suzukii Shiraki, 1913: 610 (*Hammoderes*)

must be:

suzukii Shiraki, 1913: 611 (*Hammoderus*)

p. 413

printed:

holzschugi Bi & Lin, 2016: 69 A: YUN

must be:

holzschuhi Bi & Lin, 2016: 69 A: YUN

p. 419

printed:

genus *Paradeucalion* Breuning, 1950b: 153 type species *Deucalion desertarum*
Wollaston, 1854

desertarum Wollaston, 1854: 430 N: MR (Desertas Is.)

must be:

genus *Paradeucalion* Breuning, 1950b: 153 type species *Deucalion desertarum*
Wollaston, 1854

desertarum Wollaston, 1854: 430 (*Deucalion*) N: MR (Desertas Is.)

maderense Krátký & Aguiar, 2019: 3 N: MR

p. 419

printed:

aurora Danilevsky, 1980: 852 A: AB GG IN ?TR

and

striatopunctata Sama, 1994f: 554 A: TR

must be

aurora Danilevsky, 1980: 852 A: AB IN

and

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

striatopunctata Sama, 1994f: 554 A: GG TR
[*samai* Özdikmen, 2021f: 1440] - unavailable name
[*sericata* Sama, 1996c: 114] - unavailable name

According to Danilevsky (2017b) Georgian populations of *Parmena aurora* Danilevsky, 1980 (described from Talysh) are very close to *P. striatopunctata* Sama, 1994f (described from Artvin). Now populations from Adzharia (Georgia) are accepted as *P. striatopunctata*.

The name *Parmena samai* Özdikmen, 2021f proposed for a female described before as *P. sericata* Sama, 1996c [unavailable name - conditional proposal] is also unavailable, as no description of a new species was published.

p. 425

printed:

alexandrovi Plavilstshikov, 1915c: 109 (*Oberea*) A: FE JIL

must be:

alexandrovi Plavilstshikov, 1915c: 109 (*Oberea*) A: FE JIL

infrequens Cherepanov, 1996: 136

Oberea alexandrovi var. *infrequens* Plavilstshikov, 1915c was an unavailable name, described from same population as the nominative form; “its author expressly gave it infrasubspecific rank” according to the Article 45.6.4. of ICZN. The name was published as available later: *Oberea alexandrovi* ssp. *infrequens* Cherepanov, 1996.

pp. 427 and 431

The record of *Oberea pedemontana* Chevrolat, 1856 for Turkey by Breuning (1960b), as var. *koniensis* Breuning, 1960b was rejected by Sama (2002) and Sama & Löbl (2010), but accepted by Özdikmen (2021d).

The record of *Oberea euphorbiae* (Germar, 1813) for “Konstantinopel” by Plavilstshikov (1927d) and repeated by Breuning (1962f) was accepted by Özdikmen (2021d) as real.

p. 428

printed:

imbrevicollis Pic, 1928d: 16

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

must be:

inbrevicollis Pic, 1928d: 16

p. 428

printed:

curialis Pascoe, 1866b: 264 A: CH ORR

nonfriedi Pic, 1923a: 14

must be:

curialis Pascoe, 1866b: 264 A: CH ORR

brevicollis Pascoe, 1867b: 420

nonfriedi Pic, 1923a: 14

p. 430

printed:

ishigakiana Matsushita, 1941: 158 A: JA (Ryukyus)

must be:

isigakiana Matsushita, 1941: 158 A: JA (Ryukyus)

p. 431

printed:

scutellaroides Breuning, 1947c: 58 [RN] A: BEI FE NC SC ZHE

#63 #400

chinensis Tsherepanov, 1985: 147 [RN]

licenti Pic, 1939b: 3 [Chine: Fei hien]

scutellaris Fairmaire, 1888b: 147 [HN]

must be:

licenti Pic, 1939b: 3 [Chine: Fei hien] A: BEI FE NC SC ZHE

chinensis Tsherepanov, 1985: 147 [RN]

scutellaris Fairmaire, 1888b: 147 [HN]

scutellaroides Breuning, 1947c: 58 [RN]

According to the photos (arranged by Dr. A. Mantilleri and Mr. Ch. Rivier) of the types (holotype-male and paratype-female) of *Oberea coreana* var. *licenti* Pic, 1939b (“Fei hien, 19.6.36”) preserved in Muséum national d’Histoire naturelle (Paris), the specimens traditionally published as *Oberea scutellaroides* Breuning, 1947c (= *Oberea chinensis* Tsherepanov, 1985) must be identified as *Oberea licenti* Pic, 1939b, so *Oberea coreana* var. *licenti* Pic, 1939b = *Oberea scutellaroides* Breuning, 1947c, **syn. nov.**

According to Mei-Ying Lin (personal message, 26.05.2022): “Fei Hien = Shandong Province, Linyi City, Feixian (Fei County)”.

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 433

printed:

duponcheli Brullé, 1832: 260 (*Saperda*) **E:** AL BU MC GR

must be:

duponcheli Brullé, 1832: 260 (*Saperda*) **E:** AL BU MC GR

p. 434

missing name:

Phytoecia (Cinctophytoecia) approximata Pu, 1992b: 613, 621 **A:** YUN

p. 435

printed:

flavescens Brullé, 1832: 262 (*Saperda*) **A:** AL GR MC

must be:

flavescens Brullé, 1832: 262 (*Saperda*) **E:** AL GR MC

p. 436

printed:

affinis boeberi Ganglbauer, 1884: 559 [RN] [“Caucasus, Turkei”] **E:** ST **A:** AB AR GG IN TR

flavipes Gyllenhal, 1817: 436 (nota -“Caucaso”) [HN]

must be:

affinis boeberi Ganglbauer, 1884: 559 [RN] [“Caucasus, Türkei”] **E:** ST **A:** AB AR GG IN TR

flavipes Gyllenhal, 1817: 436 (*Saperda*) - nota -“Caucaso” [HN]

p. 438

printed:

lineatocollis Levrat, 1859: 35

must be:

lineatocollis Levrat, 1859: 35

p. 439

Phytoecia (Opsilia) coerulescens (Scopoli, 1763) was recorded (Tsherepanov, 1985: 203) for East Siberia (Tuva).

p. 439

Phytoecia uncinata was recorded for Turkey (Izmir) by Özdikmen et al. (2005).

p. 440

printed:

albovittigera Heyden, 1863: 130 **E**: BU GR MC TR **A**: TR

languida Fairmaire, 1865: 177 (*Coptosia*) [HN]

semiannulicornis Pic, 1936c: 4 (*Coptosia*)

vittigera Fairmaire, 1868a: pl. 54, fig. 256 (*Coptosia*)

must be:

albovittigera Heyden, 1863: 130 **E**: BU GR MC TR **A**: TR

languida Fairmaire, 1865: 177 (*Coptosia*) [HN]

reichei Kraatz, 1876c: 287 (*Coptosia*)

semiannulicornis Pic, 1936c: 4 (*Coptosia*)

vittigera Fairmaire, 1868a: pl. 54, fig. 256 (*Coptosia*)

p. 440

printed:

piciana Jakovlev, 1924c: 239 [RN]

must be:

piciana Jakobson, 1924: 239 [RN]

p. 440

printed:

urartica Kasatkin, 2015b: 43 **A**: TR

must be:

urartica Kasatkin, 2015b: 43 **A**: AB IN TR

p. 442

printed:

longicollis Costa, 1878: 27

must be:

longicollis Costa, 1875: 27

p. 443

printed:

melanocera Gmelin, 1790: 1838 (*Cerambyx*)

must be:

melanoceras Gmelin, 1790: 1838 (*Cerambyx*)

p. 443

printed:

hispancia Breuning, 1951a: 364

must be:

hispanica Breuning, 1951a: 364

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

“*hispancia*” - wrong original spelling (misprint), see correct spelling in the Index, p. 458

p. 445-446

printed:

subgenus *Pseudopilemia* Kasatkin, 2018: 157 type species *Saperda hirsutula* Frölich, 1793

buglanica D. Marklund & S. Marklund, 2014: 276 **A: TR #241**

evae D. Marklund & S. Marklund, 2014: 274 **A: TR**

ghobarii Danilevsky, 2018b: 589 (*Phytoecia*) **A: IN**

hirsutula hirsutula Frölich, 1793: 141 (*Saperda*) **E: AL BH BU CR GR HU KZ MC MD ME RO SB SK SL ST UK A: AB AR GG IN IS JO LE KZ SY TR WS**

androsensis Breuning, 1963a: 10 (*Oxyilia*)

atomaria Townson, 1797: 470 (*Saperda*)

ciliciae Breuning, 1951a: 406 (*Phytoecia*)

holosericea Faldermann, 1837: 287 (*Saperda*)

obsoleta Ganglbauer, 1889d: 487

tournieri Pic, 1952a: 2

hirsutula homoiesthes Ganglbauer, 1888d: 197 **A: IN TM**

konyaensis Danilevsky, 2010e: 20 **A: TR**

kruszelnickii Szczepański & Karpiński, 2017: 142 **E: GR**

must be:

subgenus *Pseudopilemia* Kasatkin, 2018: 157 type species *Saperda hirsutula* Frölich, 1793

ghobarii Danilevsky, 2018b: 589 (*Phytoecia*) **A: IN**

hirsutula hirsutula Frölich, 1793: 141 (*Saperda*) [“Oesterreich”] **E: AL BH BU CR GR HU KZ MC MD ME RO SB SK SL ST UK A: AB AR GG IN IS JO LE KZ SY TR WS**

androsensis Breuning, 1963a: 10 (*Oxyilia*) - Grèce : Ile d'Andros

atomaria Townson, 1797: 470 (*Saperda*) - Hungary

buglanica D.Marklund & S.Marklund, 2014: 276 (*Phytoecia*) - Bingöl #241

ciliciae Breuning, 1951a: 406 (*Phytoecia*)

evae D.Marklund & S.Marklund, 2014: 274 (*Phytoecia*) - Bingöl

holosericea Faldermann, 1837: 287 (*Saperda*) - “Transcaucasia”

obsoleta Ganglbauer, 1889d: 487 - “Transcaucasien, Pontus”.

tournieri Pic, 1952a: 2 (*Phytoecia*) - Sicile

hirsutula homoiesthes Ganglbauer, 1888d: 197 **A: IN TM**

konyaensis Danilevsky, 2010e: 20 **A: TR**

kruszelnickii Szczepański & Karpiński, 2017: 142 (*Phytoecia*) **E: GR**

p. 445

Pilemia tigrina was recorded many times for Turkey: Heyden (1888 - Malatia), Bodemeyer (1906 - Bilecik), Demelt & Alkan (1962 - Izmir), Demelt (1963 - Izmir), Sama (2002 - “Asia Minor, Middle East”) and others.

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 448

printed:

subgenus *Prosopocera* Blanchard, 1845: 160 type species *Lamia fronticornis* Fabricius, 1781 (= *Cerambyx bipunctatus* Drury, 1773)

Anoplostetha Dejean, 1835: 341 type species *Lamia lactator* Fabricius, 1801

Hagesata Pascoe, 1864c: 275 type species *Hagesata foxcrofti* Pascoe, 1864

Imalmus Pascoe, 1864c: 276 type species *Imalmus capito* Pascoe, 1864

Zalates J. Thomson, 1860: 376 type species *Zalates callipyga* J. Thomson, 1860

albescens Breuning, 1938e: 110 A: SA

must be:

subgenus *Alphitopola* J.Thomson, 1857f: 299 type species *Aphitopola lactea* J. Thomson, 1857

Anybostetha Quedenfeldt, 1888: 201 type species *Anybostetha saperdoides* Quedenfeldt, 1888

Hodoeporus J.Thomson, 1858: 188 type species not specified

Galactesthes Fairmaire, 1897b: 152 type species *Galactesthes nivosus* Fairmaire, 1897

Lepesmia Breuning, 1956g: 672 type species *Lepesmia rufula* Breuning, 1956

Parachariesthoides Breuning, 1976e: 1033 type species *Parachariesthoides allaeri* Breuning, 1976

Pseuderemon Breuning, 1966i: 181 type species *Pseuderemon bifuscomaculipennis* Breuning, 1966

Scapochariesthoides Breuning, 1974k: 111 type species *Scapochariesthoides macrophthalma* Breuning, 1974

Zalatida Fähræus, 1872b: 33 type species *Zalatida paykullii* Fähræus, 1872

***unicolor* Gahan, 1898: 52 (*Alphitopola*) A: SA AFR**

albescens Breuning, 1938e: 110

parvula Breuning, 1934: 90

patriziana Breuning, 1934: 89

p. 449

Anaches dorsalis (Pascoe, 1858) was recorded for Kashmir (as *Pterolophia*) by Breuning (1961d).

p. 449

printed:

genus *Alidus* Gahan, 1893a: 258 type species *Alidus biplagiatus* Gahan, 1893

biplagiatus Gahan, 1893a: 258 A: GUA NP YUN **ORR #400**

must be:

genus *Alidus* Gahan, 1893a: 258 type species *Alidus biplagiatus* Gahan, 1893

Paramispila Breuning, 1959b: 75 type species *Aphelocnemis bispeularis* White, 1858
bispeularis White, 1858b: 401 (*Aploenemia*) A: GUA NP YUN **ORR**

biplagiatus Gahan, 1893a: 258 **#400**

The synonymy was established by Heller (1926).

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 450

printed:

subgenus *Nijimaia* Matsushita, 1933b: 386 type species *Nijimaia bifasciana* Matsushita, 1933

Baeckmanella Shabliovsky, 1936: 186 type species *Baeckmanella iljinskyi* Shabliovsky, 1936 (= *Nijimaia bifasciana* Matsushita, 1933)

Pseudenispia Breuning, 1938c type species *Pseudenispia albomarmorata* Breuning, 1938c

must be:

subgenus *Nijimaia* Matsushita, 1933b: 386 type species *Nijimaia bifasciana* Matsushita, 1933

Baeckmanella Shabliovsky, 1936: 186 type species *Baeckmanella iljinskyi* Shabliovsky, 1936 (= *Nijimaia bifasciana* Matsushita, 1933)

Pseudenispia Breuning, 1938c: 388 was published as available name with type species *Pseudenispia albomarmorata* Breuning, 1938c by Makihara (2007b: 555). The name was originally introduced for 4 species without type-species designation, and so unavailable (Art. 13.3.).

pp. 450 and 461

printed (p. 450):

bhutanensis Breuning, 1975d: 338 (*Similosodus*) A: BT

and (p. 461)

bhutanensis Breuning, 1975d: 338 A: BT

Second case was wrong.

p. 451

printed:

subgenus *Mispila* Pascoe, 1864a: 58 type species *Mispila venosa* Pascoe, 1864

Diatylus Lacordaire, 1872: 552 type species *Diatylus zonarius* Lacordaire, 1872 (= *Mispila curvilinea* Pascoe, 1869)

curvilinea Pascoe, 1869b: 206 A: AP GUX YUN **ORR** #126

multilineatus Pic, 1925a: 24 (*Alidus*)

zonaria Lacordaire, 1872: 365 (*Diatylus*)

must be:

subgenus *Mispila* Pascoe, 1864a: 58 type species *Mispila venosa* Pascoe, 1864

Diatylus Lacordaire, 1872: 552 type species *Diatylus zonarius* Lacordaire, 1872 (= *Mispila curvilinea* Pascoe, 1869)

curvilinea Pascoe, 1869b: 206 A: AP GUX YUN **ORR** #126

multilineata Pic, 1925a: 24 (*Alidus*)

Mispila zonaria (Lacordaire, 1872) sensu Breuning (1973c) is a valid name of an Oriental species.

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 452

printed:

subgenus *Hammatoniphona* Pic, 1936: 31 type species *Camptocnema longicornis*
Pic, 1926

must be:

subgenus *Hamatoniphona* Pic, 1936: 31 type species *Camptocnema longicornis*
Pic, 1926

p. 455

printed:

tuberculatrix Fabricius, 1781 (*Lamia*) A: AP **AFR ORR #166**

must be:

tuberculato~~r~~ Fabricius, 1781 (*Lamia*) A: AP **AFR ORR #166**

p. 456

printed:

rondoiana Breuning, 1963k: 54 A: SCH **ORR #400**

must be:

rondo~~i~~ana Breuning, 1963k: 54 A: SCH **ORR #400**

p. 461

printed:

bankii Fabricius, 1775: 176 (*Lamia*) A: GUA HAI JA (Ogasawara Isls.) TAI **AUR ORR**

hollandicus Boisduval, 1835: 491 (*Acanthocinus*)

insularis Pascoe, 1859: 39 (*Niphona*)

iratus Pascoe, 1862b: 464 (*Niphona*)

miscellus Pascoe, 1863b: 529 (*Niphona*)

musivus Pascoe, 1864a: 65 (*Aegomomus*)

nutans Sharp, 1878: 209 (*Micracantha*)

torosus Pascoe, 1864b: 223 (*Niphona*)

uchiyamai Matsushita, 1935: 120

vaulo~~g~~eri Pic, 1925a: 28 (*Zaera*)

must be:

bankii Fabricius, 1775: 176 (*Lamia*) A: GUA HAI JA (Ogasawara Isls.) TAI **AUR ORR**

dentata Olivier, 1797: 469 (*Lamia*)

desjardinsii Fairmaire, 1889b: xcvi (*Micracantha*)

hollandicus Boisduval, 1835: 491 (*Acanthocinus*)

insularis Pascoe, 1859: 39 (*Niphona*)

iratus Pascoe, 1862b: 464 (*Niphona*)

madecassa Künckel, 1890: pl. 50, fig. 5 (*Micracantha*)

miscellus Pascoe, 1863b: 529 (*Niphona*)

musivus Pascoe, 1864a: 65 (*Aegomomus*)

nutans Sharp, 1878: 209 (*Micracantha*)

obliquata Fairmaire, 1896b: 386 (*Micracantha*)

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

spinipes Olivier, 1800: N° 67, 103 (*Cerambyx*)

spinipes Fabricius, 1801: 282 (*Lamia*)

torosus Pascoe, 1864b: 223 (*Niphona*)

uchiyamai Matsushita, 1935: 120 (*Rhytiphora*)

vauloegeri Pic, 1925a: 28 (*Zaeera*)

Künckel d'Hercule M. 1890: Histoire Naturelle des Coléoptères. In: Grandidier A.:
Histoire Physique, Naturelle et Politique de Madagascar 22 (2) Atlas 1: 54 pls.

pp. 461-462

printed (p. 461):

genus *Sthenias* Laporte, 1840: 466 type species *Lamia grisator* Fabricius, 1787

and (p. 462)

subgenus *Sthenias* Laporte, 1840: 466 type species *Lamia grisator* Fabricius, 1787

must be (p. 461):

genus *Sthenias* Dejean, 1835: 344 type species *Lamia grisator* Fabricius, 1787

and (p. 462)

subgenus *Sthenias* Dejean, 1835: 344 type species *Lamia grisator* Fabricius, 1787

p. 463

printed:

japonica Tamanuki, 1927: 124

must be:

japonica Tamanuki, 1927: 124 (*Paraglenea*)

p. 464

printed:

sedecimpunctata sedecimpunctata Motschulsky, 1860b: 151 (*Saperda*) A: ES FE

HEI HEB ?HUB JA JIL LIA NC SC SHA #179

carinata Blessig, 1873: 219 (*Saperda*)

duodecimpunctata Motschulsky, 1860b: 151 (*Saperda*) [HN]

motschulskyi Plavilstshikov, 1915b: 80 (*Saperda*) [RN]

rosinae Pic, 1904d: 17 (*Saperda*)

variicornis Bates, 1884a: 256

must be:

sedecimpunctata sedecimpunctata Motschulsky, 1860b: 151 (*Saperda*) A: ES FE

HEI HEB ?HUB JA JIL LIA NC SC SHA #179

carinata Blessig, 1873: 219 (*Saperda*)

duodecimpunctata Motschulsky, 1860b: 151 (*Saperda*) [HN]

motschulskyi Plavilstshikov, 1915b: 80 (*Saperda*) [RN]

rosinae Pic, 1904d: 17 (*Saperda*)

sulphurata Matsumura, 1906: 141 n 698, pl. 52, fig. 13 (*Saperda*) [HN]

variicornis Bates, 1884a: 256

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 466

printed:

diana diana J. Thomson, 1865: 561 A: YUN **ORR**

theresae Pic, 1943c: 15

must be:

diana diana J. Thomson, 1865: 561 A: YUN **ORR**

bimaculiceps Gahan, 1889: 215

theresae Pic, 1943c: 15

p. 466

printed:

fainanensis fainanensis Pic, 1916e: 17 A: TAI

must be:

fainanensis Pic, 1916e: 17 A: TAI

p. 468

printed:

pulchella Pascoe, 1858: 260 A: SD **ORR** #280

vesta Pascoe, 1866: 260

vestalis Heller, 1934: 284

must be:

pulchella Pascoe, 1858: 260 A: SD **ORR** #280

vesta Pascoe, 1866: 260

According to Hiremath & Lin (2021), *Glenea vestalis* Heller, 1934 is a valid name of a species known from Philippines.

p. 470

printed:

guedalcanalana Breuning, 1958g: 315 (*Glenea*)

must be:

guedalcanalana Breuning, 1958g: 315 (*Glenea*)

p. 476

printed:

rufina Pascoe, 1858: 259 A: GUX YUN **ORR**

dichroma J. Thomson, 1865: 560

griseescens Pic, 1928b: 22

laosensis Pic, 1925a: 32

obsoleta J. Thomson, 1860: 60

must be:

rufina Pascoe, 1858: 259 A: GUX YUN **ORR**

griseescens Pic, 1928b: 22

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

laosensis Pic, 1925a: 32
obsoleta J. Thomson, 1860: 60

Sibara dichroma J. Thomson, 1865 is a valid name of an Oriental species (see: Lin & Tavakilian, 2019).

p. 478

printed:

praeustus praeustus Linnaeus, 1758: 399 (*Leptura*) **E**: AL AU BE BH BU BY CR CT CZ DE EN FI FR GB GE GR HU IR IT LA LS LT LU MC MD ME NL NR NT PL PT RO SB SK SL SL SP ST SV SZ TR UK **A**: AB AR ES GG KZ MG SY TR WS **#464**

inapicalis Pic, 1891b: 37

pilosus Geoffroy, 1785: 78 (*Leptura*) [HN]

praecestus Dufour, 1843: 101 (*Saperda*)

ustulatus Hagenbach, 1822: 11 (*Saperda*)

must be:

praeustus praeustus Linnaeus, 1758: 399 (*Leptura*) **E**: AL AU BE BH BU BY CR CT CZ DE EN FI FR GB GE GR HU IR IT LA LS LT LU MC MD ME NL NR NT PL PT RO SB SK SL SL SP ST SV SZ TR UK **A**: AB AR ES GG KZ MG SY TR WS **#464**

inapicalis Pic, 1891b: 37

pilosus Geoffroy, 1785: 78 (*Leptura*) [HN]

ustulatus Hagenbach, 1822: 11 (*Saperda*)

The name *Saperda praecesta*, Dufour, 1843: 101 (originally published as “*S. praecesta*. F.”) was not a new name, but wrong spelling of *Saperda praeusta* Fabricius, and so unavailable.

p. 479

printed:

genus *Cherochariesthes* Téocchi, 1989: 10 type species *Pseudochariesthes variegata* Breuning, 1939

holzschuhi Téocchi, 1989: 11 (*Freapomecyna*) **A**: SA YE

must be:

genus *Kerochariesthes* Téocchi, 1990b: 19 type species *Pseudochariesthes variegata* Breuning, 1939

Cherochariesthes, Lóbl & Smetana, 2010: 333 (misspelling)

holzschuhi Téocchi, 1992: 300 (*Freapomecyna*) **A**: SA YE

holzschuhi Teocchi, 1990a: 11 (*Freapomecyna*) (nomen nudum)

Téocchi P. 1990a: Notes concernant la systématique et la bionomie de quelques Lamiaires africains. *Bulletin de la Société Sciences Nat* **63** (1989): 9-12.

Téocchi P. 1990b: Diagnoses et rectifications systématiques concernant quelques

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

Lamiaires africains (Coleoptera Cerambycidae Lamiinae). *Bulletin de la Société Sciences Nat* **64** [1989]: 19-22, 6 figs.

pp. 494, 502, 504

Several references must be included:

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Breuning S. 1966i: Nouveaux Lamiaires du Musée Royal de l'Afrique centrale (Coleoptera Cerambycidae). *Revue de Zoologie et de Botanique Africaines* **74** (1-2): 175-183.

Breuning S. 1974k: Descriptions de Lamiaires nouveaux d'Afrique (Coleoptera Cerambycidae). *Revue de Zoologie et de Botanique Africaines* **88** (1): 111-114.

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p. 523

missing reference:

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p. 555

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Heller K.M. 1926b: Systematische und faunistische Notizen über Käfer, nebst einem neuen Colpodes. *Entomologische Mitteilungen* **15** (2): 195-196.

p. 561

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Holzschuh C. 1991d: [new taxa]. In: Holzschuh C. & Téocchi P.: Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) of Saudi Arabia: Parft I, Lamiinae. *Fauna of Saudi Arabia* **12**: 295-311.

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Holzschuh C. 1992b: Neue Bockkäfer aus Europa und Asien III, 57 neue Bockkäfer aus Asien, vorwiegend aus China, Thailand und Vietnam (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). *FBVA Berichte - Schriftenreihe der Forstlichen Bundesversuchsanstalt in Wien* **69**: 1-66.

M.L. Danilevsky, G. Tavakilian

p. 568

printed:

Jakobson G.G. 1924c

must be:

Jakobson G.G. 1924

p. 572

printed:

Kiseleva, E.F. 1927: O zhykakh – usachakh (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) okrestnostey g. Tomsk. *Izvestiya Tomskogo Gosudarstvennogo Universiteta* **77** [1926]: 123–133.

Kisselew, E.F. 1926: Ueber Bockkäfer der Umgegend von Tomsk. [*Transactions of the Tomsk State University*] **77**: 123–133.

must be:

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p. 575

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p. 576

missing reference:

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p. 578

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p. 659

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must be:

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p. 666

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pp. 667-668

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p. 692

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Zaitzev D. A. 1937:

must be:

Zaitzev D. W. 1937:

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